

KG-11366. 000-873

KG11366

000	Measures of Variables in ^{Island} M15, E.F.L., No. 53	1917
001	" " E.F.L., No. 52	1916-1917
002	" " E.F.L., No. 54	1917-1918
003	" " E.F.L., No. 55	1917-1918
004	Observing Book, E.F.L., No. 56	1918-
005	" " E.F.L., No. 57	1918
006	Long Exposure H.S. Regions + Series E.F.L., No. 58	1918- 1919
007	Measures of the New Satellite of Saturn + No. Polar Segment, ^{H.S.} E.F.L., No. 29	1904-1911
008	M Determinations - " North Pole Plates E.F.L., No. 59	1918-1919
009	" " E.F.L., No. 60	1919-
010	" " E.F.L., No. 61	1919-1920
011	" " E.F.L., No. 62	1919-1920
012	" " E.F.L., No. 63	1920
013	MF Series E.F.L., No. 64	1920
014	" " E.F.L., No. 65	1920-1921
015	" " E.F.L., No. 66	1921
016	MC + A Plates E.F.L., No. 67	1921
017	Large Magellanic Cloud E.F.L., No. 68	1921-1922
018	MC Plates H.S.L., No. 1	1915-1916
019	" " H.S.L., No. 2	1915-1916
020	" " H.S.L., No. 3	1916
	(H.S. Locke)	
021	MC Plates H.S.L., No. 4	1916, 1918
022	MC Plates H.S.L., No. 5	1916-1917
023	" " H.S.L., No. 6	1917
024	Misc. Plates (A.C., etc.) H.S.L., No. 7	1917-1918
025	MC Plates H.S.L., No. 8	1917-1918
026	MC Plates H.S.L., No. 9	1917-1918
027	B + MC Plates H.S.L., No. 10	1917-1918
028	Observing Book JCM, No. 1 (A.J.C.)	1910-1911
029	" " (Scale Measures) JCM, No. 2	1913-1914
030	" " (M.D. Plates) JCM, No. 3	1913-1914

GFM = Genevieve F. Mathews

ACM = A.C. Maury

MOR = M.E. O'Reilly

KG11366

031	Observing Book (Misc. Plates)	JCM, No. 5	1918-1919
032	B Series	JCM, No. 7	1919
033	Observing Book (B Series)	JCM, No. 8	1919
034	Observing Book (Misc. Measures)	MK? No. 9	1919-1920
035	Novae? (Maps of the Sky, Ac Plates)	MK No. 10	1919-1920
036	Observing Book, Variable Stars, Etc.	GFM, No. 1	1912-1913
037	" , Scale Measures,	GFM, No. 2	1913
038	" , Series Measures,	GFM, No. 3	1913-1916
039	" , Series, Etc.,	GFM, No. 4	1914
040	" , Miscellaneous,	GFM, No. 5	1914-1915
041	Circumpolar Variables ,	GFM, No. 7	1914-1915
042	" (Est. of Magn.)	GFM, No. 8	1914-1915
043	Series Measures (Principally "blue" plates)	GFM, No. 9	1915
044	" ("yellow" ")	GFM, No. 10	1915-1916
045	Circumpolar Variables	GFM, No. 6	1914-1916
046	" " (Est. of brightness)	GFM, No. 11	1915-1916
047	" " " (overlows book)	GFM, No. 12	1915
048	Circumpolar Variables	GFM, No. 13	1916
049	" (Record of observations on Photographs)	GFM, No. 14	1916
050	Tables of Ursa Majoris	, Miss Maury,	1894-1896
051	Rotation of Primary Star & Separation of Satellites,	ACM,	1928-1932
052	Formulas for Reduction, Phases in H.A. 848 [*] ,	ACM	1918-1922
053	(Loose Papers) β Lyrae H.A. 848 + others,	ACM ^{annals "The Spectral Changes of β Lyrae".}	1933
054	Observing Book, Meas. of Variables + Standard Sequences,	MOR, No. 1	1912
055	Misc. observations, Meas. Variables, etc.	MOR, No. 2	1914-1917
056	Obs. Book - Scale Measures of Standard Regions on I's' Plates,	MOR, No. 3	1913-14
057	" - Circumpolar Variables, Scale Meas. of Comp. Stars	MOR, No. 4	1914
058	" - MC Plates,	MOR, No. 5	1914
059	Meas. of Misc. Plates	MOR, No. 6	1914
060	"	MOR, No. 7	1914

MORS - ~~Philip~~ O'Reilly Sloan
(name change between #28 + #29)

PGOR - P.G. O'Reilly
(Philip)

K6 11366

061	Obs. Bk - MC + Misc. Plates	MOR	No. 8	1914
062	" - "	MOR	No 9	1914
063	" "	MOR	No 10	1914-1915
064	" - "	MOR	No 11	1914-15
065	" "	MOR	No 12	1915-1916
066	" "	MOR	No 13	1915
067	" "	MOR	No 14	1915
068	" "	MOR	No 15	1915
069	" "	MOR	No 16	1915
070	" "	MOR	No 17	1915-16
071	Obs. Bk. - Southern + AS Plates	MOR	No 18	1915-1916
072	" MC + Misc. Plates	MOR	No 19	1916-1917
073	" - Misc.	MOR	No 20	1916-1917
074	Obs. Bk.	MOR	No 21	1916-1917
075	" - Southern Plates	MOR	No 22	1916
076	Obs. Bk. - Mostly Southern Regions	MOR	No 23	1916
077	" "	MOR	No 24	1916-17
078	" "	MOR	No 25	1917
079	" "	MOR	No. 26	1917
080	" - Misc.	MOR	No. 27	1917-18
081	" "	MOR	No 28	1917-1918
082	Observing Book	MORS	No 29	1918
083	" - Scale Measures.	MORS	No 30	1918
084	" - B Series	MORS	No 31	1918
085	" - Cat. Sc. Measures	MORS	No. 32	1918
086	" - For Cat. 1° Square	MORS	No. 33	1918
087	" - Cat 4° Square	MORS	No 34	1918
088	" (Probably same as 8")	PGOR	No. 1 (?)	1910-12
089	8" Polar Equatorial	PGOR	No 2	1912-1913
090	8" " (Obs of Variables)	PGOR	No 3	1913

CHP = C. H. Payne
(Cecelia)

K6 11366

091	Various Plate Measurements	CHP	No 1	
092	"	CHP	No 2	
093	"	CHP	No 3	
094	"	CHP	No 4	
095	Wave Length Calculations	CHP	No 5	
096	Apertured MC plates	CHP	No 6	
097	Emission lines, Apertured Spectra	CHP	No 7	
098	Apertured Arcturus Vega	CHP	No 8	c. 1926?
099	Microphotometer, General	CHP	No 9	
100	Apertured Altair, Betelgeuse	CHP	No 10	
101	Apertured c Stars + others	CHP	No 11	
102	Single Spectra, (Capella, Rigel, Sirius, Altair)	CHP	No 12	
103	Apertured β Cas	CHP	No 13	
104	General Ledgers	CHP	No 14	
105	Line Photometry	CHP	No 15	
106	Gaertner	CHP	No 16	
107	Line Photometry	CHP	No 17	
108	Plates	CHP	No 18	
109	Apertured ^(Line Photometry) Mira & Cygni & Persei	CHP	No 20	
110	Pleides Background	CHP	No 22	
111	Line Mira 3 UMa Summary	CHP	No 24	
112	K Stars	CHP	No 25	
113	Angstrom Magnitudes	CHP	No 26	
114	Schilt Microphotometer	CHP	No 27	
115	C Stars	CHP	No 28	
116	C- Stars	CHP	No 29	
117	"	CHP	No 30	
118	B- Stars	CHP	No 31	
119	C- Stars	CHP	No 32	
120	Temperatures	CHP	No 35	

MLM = Mary L. Miller (work under C. H. Payne)
 HML = H. M. Lewis (under C. H. Payne)

Cecelia H. Payne-Gaposchkin
 MRD = M. R. Dwyer (work under C. H. Payne)

ECP = E. C. Pickering
 EEB = E. E. Barnard
 Fr. = Frank Taldo

Mohr
 J.S. = J. Smith

KG 11366

121 121	Misc.	CHP	No 36	
122	Line Areas	CHP	No 37	
123	Long Disp. Spectrophotometry	CHP	No 38	
124	Line Areas	CHP	No 39	
125	K-Stars	CHP	No 40	
126	Line Contours, O Stars	CHP	No 42	
127	μ of c-stars	CHP	No 43	
128.1	Identifications (Sequences)	CHP	No 52	
128	Various Plate Measurements	MRD	No 56	
128 129	"	MLM	No 56	
		MLM	No 57	
129 130	"	HML	No 57	
130 131	"	Mohr	No 58	
131 132	Ptm Grating, Cluster Maps, Sequences	?	No 61	
132 133	Measures by Bond Astronomical Club under	CHP	Bond 1	1928
135	134 Various Plate Measures	?	?	?
	Misc.	ECP		1877
135 136	Misc. Correspondence	EEB		1898
136		EEB		1877
137	Diagrams, Sequences	CHP?	No 61	
138 137	Progress of Draper Catalogue	?	No 11	?
140	138 Misc.	?	—	—
	139 Various Plate Measures	—	—	1890-91
	140 Misc. Counts for Annual Report	ECP	No 1	1899-1900
A1	"	ECP	No 2	1908-1909
142	Misc. Memoranda	ECP	No 1	1902-1903
143	"	ECP	No 2	1888-1895
144	Accident Book	ECP		1905-1906
145	Notebook	?	No 2	—
146	Eye Estimates of Stellar Magnitudes Instructions J.S.			1881
147	Plates + Observations	—	—	—
148	Measures + Misc.	ECP?	—	—
149	Eye piece Measurements	Fr.		1877
150	Financial Record + other Computations	ECP?		1906

L.S.S. = L.S. Schuetz
 D.E. Stewart = D.S.
 R.S. = Rufus Suter
 W.E. Winslow Epton
 M.H.V. - Mary ~~Hassaltine~~ ^{Hata} Varn
 I.E.W. - Ida Woods
 H.W. = H.H. Plaskett
 ARS - AR Sawyer
 W.H.P. = W.H. Pickering
 SR = Susan Raymond
 WAR - WA Rogers (under H.H. Plaskett)
 L.W. - Leonard Waldo

KG 11366

151	Eclipse Note Book			1888-90
152	Determinations of PH ^{Parallax} by PHTG. Means	WHP	Notebook E No 45	1882
153	Preparations for Observing Total Eclipse	WHP	No 44	1886
154	Various Essays	WHP		1878
155	"	WHP		1879
156	Variables + Asteroids	SR	No 1	1914-16
157	Solar Series Measures, Sunoma Scale Meas.	SR	No 2	1916
158	Circumpolar Variables	SR	No 3	1916
159	Asteroids	SR	No 4	1911 + 1917
160	Asteroids Misc-	SR	No 5	1917
		WAR		1875
161	Misc Observations	WAR		1875
162	Plates (Uora Aquilae)	ARS		1918
163	M-determinations	ARS		-
164	Variable Star Observations	LSS		1909
165	Observations of Nebulae	DS.		1900
166	Plate Measures	R.S.		1923
167	"			
168	Observations + Calc. Rel. to Ecographical Position	WEL		1897
169	Latitude + Longitude, Anquipa Station	WEL	No. 9	1896
170	Misc. Scale Measures on Series + Chart Plates	MHV	No 1	1917-18
171	Observations of Novae	MHV	No 2	1917
172	"	MHV	No 3	1918-
173	"	MHV	No 4	1918
174	Double Star Measures	L.W.	No 1	1876
175	Correspondence	AW.		1896
176	Observations - Six inch Telescope	I.E.W.		1911-13
177	SS. Cygia	I.E.W.		1917
178	Instructions, Etc.	I.E.W.	No 1	1915
179	6" Telescope Observations	I.E.W.		1913-1
180	Cluster Variables	I.E.W.	No. 4	1916

KG 11366

181	Cluster Variables	IEW	No 5	1917-18
182	"	"	No 6	1919-25
183	Examination of AM and AC plates	"	No 7	1919
184	Discussion, Measures, etc. of objects suspected as Novae	"	No 8	1919
185	Examination of AM + AC plates	"	No 9	1919-20
186	Objects looked up for outsiders by request	"	No 10	1921
187	Discussion, measures, etc of New Variables	"	No 11	1921-22
188	Examination of AM + AC plates	"	No 12	1920
189	Examination of Northern Regions	"	No 13	1920
190	Examination of AM + AC plates	"	No 14	1920
			No 15	
191	"	"	No 15	1920-21
192	Discussion, Measures, etc. of objects suspected as Novae	"	No 16	1921
193	Examination of Special objects	"	No 17	1922
194	Examination of Southern Regions	"	No 18	1922
195	New Variables	"	No 19	1912-3
196	Special Examination of MC Plates	"	No. 20	1922-23
197	Discussion, measures of Nebulae + Asteroids	"	No. 21	1923
198	Cluster Variables	"	No. 22	1923
199	"	"	No. 23	1922-23
200	Special Examination of M.C. Plates	"	No 24	1923
			No 25	
201	Objects looked up for outsiders by H.C.O.	"	No. 25	1925
202	Special Examination of MC plates	"	No. 26	1921-25
203	Examination of Milky Way Regions	"	No. 27	1925-26
204	"	"	No. 28	1924-5
205	New Variables	"	No. 29	1924-26
206	Examination of Milky Way Regions	"	No. 30	1924-25
207	Cluster Variables	"	No. 31	1927
208	Misc. Milky Way Regions	"	No. 32	1925
209	Objects looked up for Outsiders	"	No 33	1902-09
210	Milky Way Regions, MC + MF Plates	"	No. 34	1926-30

J E J = J E. Jones

SMP

- 241 Meridian Photometer $\uparrow$ 1907 #11
- 242 Halley's comet observations 1909
- 243 Reduction of observations for position 1909-10, O C W & L C,
- 244 - Nova ~~Aquae~~ Aquae 1918 #3
- 245 Comparison stars 1906-09
- 246 Calculations, Schaefer & others 1905, 1911
- 247 24 inch Reflector Journal 1907 #1
- 248 Plates, photometers ~~by~~ J E J. 1935-36
- 249 RH P.T.M. 1933 #94
- 250 Various observations 1907-08
-
- 251 δ V Tauri O. Lassovszky 1925
- 252 Catterall Obs., S.C.C., 1909 #1
- 253 Meridian Photometer 1908 #12
- 254 Jup. Ec. & Var. stars. No. 22 1898 } Times & copies of measures
- 255 " " " No 23 1899 }
- 256 Discussion, Measures of Positions, etc, New Variables, I.F.W. 1926, 1928 #49
- 257 Evening Cloud Record 1916-17, #54
- 258 shade glasses, C. M. Olmsted (sp?) 1902-03
- 259 Pole plates (M.C.) and miscellaneous experiments $\uparrow$ 1928 ^{F. schilt} #60
- 260 Photometric Experiments, Ptm, 1929 #62
-
- 261 Various star observations Ptm, ⁺⁶⁰ 1929, #63
- 262 " " " Ptm, ⁺⁸⁰ 1929 #64
- 263 " " " Ptm +80, 1929 #65
- 264 " " " Ptm +70, 1929 #66
- 265 " " " Ptm ~~+~~ schilt, 1929 #67
- 266 " " " Ptm schilt, 1929 #68
- 267 " " " Ptm schilt, 1929 #69
- 268 " " " Ptm schilt, 1929 #71
- 269 " " " Ptm schilt, 1929 #72
- 270 " " " Ptm schilt, 1929 #73

271	Various star Observations	PTM, Schult	1930	#74
272	"	"	"	#75
273	RH Plates	Schult	1930	#76
274	"	"	"	#77
275	"	"	1930	#78
276	"	"	"	#79
277	"	"	1930-1	#80
278	"	"	1931	#81
279	"	"	1931	#82
280	"	"	1931	#83
			#84	
281	"	"	1931-2	#84
282	"	"	1932	#85
283	"	PTM	1932	#86
284	"	PTM	1932	#87
285	"	"	1932	#88
286	"	"	"	#89
287	"	PTM RB	"	#90
288	"	PTM RB	1932-33	#91
289	"	PTM*	1933-34	#92
290	"	PTM	1933	#93
			1933	
291	"	PTM	"	1933 #95
292	"	"	"	1933-34 #96
293	Harvard University Physics B, RH Book		1934	#97
294	RH plates	PTM RB	"	#98
295	"	PTM	"	#99
296	Equatorial Observations		1877	
297	Equatorial points, Meridian observations		1877	
298	Telescope observations		1878	
299	Reduction of photometric observations		1878	R 45
300	"	"	"	R 47

					Bk#	Vol
301	Various star observations,	Reduction of photometric	1878	#47 #50 #48	1	
302	" " "	"	1878-9	#50	1	
303	" " "	"	1879	#51	1	
304	" " "	"	1879	#54	15	
305	" " "	"	1879	#55	14	
306	" " "	"	1879-80	#91	1	
307	" " "	"	1880	#90 #92	1	
308	" " "	"	1880	#93	19	
309	" " "	"	1880-81	#95	2	
310	" " "	"	1881	#96	2	
311			1881			
311	Various star observations,	Hersch. J. Webb?	1881	#98	2	
312	" " "	"	1881	#98	2	
313	" " "	"	1882	#103	2	
314	" " "	"	1882-3	#104	3	
315	" " "	"	1883	#107	3	
316	" " "	"	1884		3	
317	" " "	"	1885		3	
318	" " "	"	1885-97			
319	" " "	"	1885-1886			
320			1886-1887			
321 a	" " "	"	1888			
321 b	" " "	"	1888			
322 a	" " "	"	1888			
322 b	" " "	"	1888-9			
323	" " "	"	1889			
324	" " "	"	1889			
325	" " "	"	1889-90		57	
326	" " "	"	1891			
327	" " "	"	1891			
328	" " "	"	1891-92		61	
329	" " "	"	1893			
330	" " "	"	1893			

		Bk#	Vol.
331	Various star observations	1894	
332		1895	
333		1895	78
334		1895	82
335		1896	83
336		1896	84
337		1896	85
338		1896	86
339		1897	87
340		1897	88
341	Various star observations	1897	89
342	" " "	1897	90
343	" " "	1897	91
344		1897	92
345		1897	93
346		1898	95
347		1898	96
348		1898	97
349		1898	98
350		1898	99
351	Various star observations	1898	100 100
352	" " "	1898	101
353	" " "	1898	102
354	" " "	1898	103
355	" " "	1899	104
356	" " "	1899	105
357	" " "	1899	106
358	" " "	1899	107
359	" " "	1899	108
360	" " "	1899	109
		1899	110

				Vol. #
361	Various Star Observations, W.A. Pickering?	1899		110
362	" " "	1899		111
363	" " "	1899		112
364	" " "	1900		113
365	" " "	1900		114
366	" " "	1900		115
367	" " "	1900		116
368	" " "	1900		117
369	" " "	1900		118
370	" " "	1900		119
371	Various Star Observations	1900		120
372	" " "	1900-01		121
373	Chronograph Record, Zone stars, 24 hr. Readings	1877		
374	Various Star Observations	1901		124
375	" " "	1901		125
376	General Catalogue, Circle Readings - Explanatory Remarks	1871-2		A ₁
377	" " " "	"		A ₂
378	" " " Polar Catalogue	1871-3		A ₃
379	Polar Catalogue, Circle Readings - Explanatory Remarks	1872-3		A ₄
380	" " " "	"		A ₅
381	" " " "	1872-3		A ₆
382	General Catalogue, Circle Readings - Explanatory Remarks	1874-5		A ₇
383	" " " "	1874-5		A ₈
384	" " " "	1874-5		A ₉
385	" " " "	1874-5		A ₁₀
386	" " " "	1874-5		A ₁₁
387	" " " "	1874-5		A ₁₂
388	Circle Readings, Fundamental stars for June	1876		A ₁₃
389	" " " "	1876		A ₁₄
390	Zone Fundamental stars, Circle Readings	1877		A ₁₅
				A ₁₆

391	Haskelyne Fundamental stars, Circle Readings	1877	A16
392	Zone " " " " " Ariadne stars, " Mars' stars & Mars	1877	A17
393	Fundamental stars, circle Readings	1878	A18
394	Coast survey Catalogue, circle Readings	1878	A19
395	Fundamental stars, circle Readings	1879	A2
396	" " " "	1879	A21
397	" " " "	1879	A22
398	" " " "	1879	A23
399	" " " "	1879-80	A24
400	" " " "	1880	A25
401	Fundamental stars, Circle Readings	1880	A26
402	" " " "	1880	A27
403	" " " "	1880	A28
404	" " " "	1880-81	A29
405	" " " "	1881	A30
406	" " " "	1881	A31
407	Fundamental stars, observations	1881	A32
408	" " " "	1881-83	A33
409	Fundamental stars, Circle Readings	1883	A34
410	" " " "	1883	A35

K611366

411	Fundamental Stars, Circle Readings	A36	1883
412	Fundamental Stars	A37	1883
413	Circle Readings (Fundamental Stars)	A38	1883-4
414	" "	A39	1884
415	Fund. & Zone Stars - Circle Readings	A40	1884-85
416	"	—	1885
417	"	A43	1885-86
418	"	—	1877
419	Observation for Inclination of Declination Wire		1878-79
420	Paris Circle Readings	B3	1879
4 421	" + Observations	B4	1879
422	"	B5	1880
423	"	B6	1880
424	Paris Observations	B7	1881-2
425	" Circle Readings	B8	1883-9
426	"	B9	1884
427	Zone Measurements	1	1882
428	Various Star Measurements ^{Revision of Equatorial zone}	2	1883
429	Revision of Equatorial Zone	3	1883
430	"	4	1883
430 431	"	5	1883
432	"	6	1883
431 432			
433	Fundamental Stars for Zones	WSR+AMB1	1870-71
434	"	" B2	1871
435	"	" B3	1871
436	"	" B4	1871
437	"	" B5	1872
438	"	" B6	1872
439	"	" B7	1872
440	" (Observations + Reductions)	"	1870-71

106 11366

441	Fundamental Stars, obs. + Reductions,	-	Vol. 511	-
442	"	-	512	-
443	"	-	F13	-
444	General Catalogue, Observations + Reductions	-	F14	1871-2
445	"	-	F15	1871
446	"	-	F16	1871-2
447	"	-	F17	1871
448	"	-	F18	1871-2
449	"	-	F19	"
450	"	-	F20	"
451	"	-	F21	"
452	"	-	F22	1872
453	"	-	F23	1872
454	"	-	F24	-
455	Polar Catalogue, Observations + Reductions	-	F25	1872-5
456	"	-	F26	"
457	"	-	F27	"
458	"	-	F28	"
459	"	-	F29	"
460	"	-	F30	"
461	"	-	F31	"
462	"	-	F32	"
463	"	-	F33	"
464	"	-	F34	"
465	"	-	F35	"
466	"	-	F36	1874-75
467	"	-	F37	-
468	General Catalogue, Obs. + Red.	-	F38	1874-75
469	"	-	F39	-
470	"	-	F40	1874-75

KG 11366

471	General Catalogue, Obs + Red.	—	F42	1874-78
472	"	—	F43	"
473	"	—	F44	"
474	"	—	F45	"
475	"	—	F46	"
476	"	—	F47	"
477	Fundamental Stars, Obs. + Red.	—	F48	1876-77
478	"	—	F49	"
479	"	—	F50	"
480	"	—	F51	"
481	"	—	F52	"
482	"	—	F53	"
483	"	—	F54	1877
484	"	+ Jones	F55	"
485	Maskekyne Fundamentals	—	F56	"
486	Madrid Circle	—	—	1875
487	Maskekyne Fundamentals	—	F57	1877
488	Fundamental Stars	—	F58	1878
489	"	—	F60	1878
490	"	—	F61	"
491	"	—	F62 F62	"
492	Coast Survey Catalogue	—	F63	1878
493	"		F64	"
494	"		F65	"
495	Miscellaneous Stars	—	F66	1878
496	Fundamental Stars		F67	1879
497	"		F68	"
498	"		F69	"
499	"		F70	"
500	"		F71	"

KG11366

501	Fundamental Stars, Obs. + Red.	- F72	1879
502	"	- F73	"
503	"	- F74	"
504	"	- F75	1880
505	"	- F76	"
506	"	- F77	"
507	"	- F78	"
508	"	- F79	"
509	"	- F80	"
510	"	- F81	"
511	"	- F82	"
512	"	- F83	1881
513	"	- F84	"
514	"	- F85	"
515	"	- F90	-
516	"	- F89	-
517	"	- F88	1881
518	"	- F87	1882
519	"	- F86	"
520	Flexure Records , Collimation, Runs	- E1	1879
521	"	- E2	1879-80
521 522	"	- E3	1880-81
522			
523	"	- E5	1881
524	"	- E6	1881-83
525	"	- E7	1883
526	"	- E8	1883-4
527	"	- E9	1884
528	"	- E10	1885-6
529	Zone Chronograph Records	- A1	1870
530	"	- A2	1870

K611366

531	Zone Chronograph Records	A3 1871.
532	"	A4 1871
533	"	A5 1871
534	"	A6 1871
535	Zone Circle Readings	C6' 1871
536	Zone Chronograph Readings	A7 1871
537	"	A8 1871-72
538	"	A9 1872
539	"	A10 1872-73
540	"	A11 1873-
541	"	A12 1873-74
541	"	A12 1873-74
542	"	A13 1874
543	"	A14 "
544	"	A15 "
545	"	A16 1874-75
546	"	A17 1875
547	"	A18 1875
548	"	A19 1875
549	"	A20 1875-76
550	"	A 21 1876
551	"	A 22 1876-77
552	"	A26 1878-79
553	"	A25 1877-78
554	"	A23 1877
555	Polaris, obs + Reduc.	B1 1879
556	"	B2 1879-80
557	"	B3 1880
558	"	B4 1880-81
559	"	B5 1881
860	"	B6 1881-83

Kt 11366

561	Polaris, Obs + Red.	B ₂	1883
562	"	B ₃	1883-84
563	"	C ₁	1870-1870
564	"	C ₂	1870-71
565	Zone Observations + Reductions	C ₃	1871
566	"	C ₄	1871
567	"	C ₅	1871
568	"	C ₆	1871
569	"	C ₇	1871
570	"	C ₈	1871
571	"	C ₉	1871
572	"	C ₁₀	1871
573	"	C ₁₁	1871
574	"	C ₁₂	1871
575 (No #75 missing?)	"	C ₁₃	1871-2
576	"	C ₁₄	1872
577	"	C ₁₅	1872-7
578	"	C ₁₆	1873
579	"	C ₁₇	1873
580	"	C ₁₈	1873-9
581	"	C ₁₉	1873
582	"	C ₂₀	1874
583	"	C ₂₁	1874
584	"	C ₂₂	1874
585	"	C ₂₃	1874
586	"	C ₂₄	"
587	"	C ₂₅	1874
588	"	C ₂₆	"
589	"	C ₂₇	1874-75
590	"	C ₂₈	1875

K611366

590	Zone Reductions	Le 28	1875
591	"	Le 29	1875
592	"	Le 30	"
593	"	Le 31	"
594	"	Le 32	"
595	"	Le 33	" - 76
596	"	Le 34	1876
597	"	Le 35	1876
598	"	Le 36	1877
599	"	Le 37	1877
600	"	Le 38	1877
		Le 39	
601	"	Le 39	1877
602	"	Le 40	1877
603	"	Le 41	1881-78
604	"	Le 42	1878
605	Zone Stars, Obs + Red.	43	1878-79
606	Zone Stars, "	Le 44	1883 -
607	" "	Le 45	1883-84
608	" "	Le 46	1884 -
609	" "	Le 47	1884-5
610	" "	Le 48	1885

KG 11366

611	Zone Stars, Obsv. + Reductions		1885
612	Fundamental Stars, Obsv. + Reductions	F no. 791	1883
613	" " " " "	no. 792	1883
614	" " " " "	no. 796	1883-84
615	" " " " "	no. 797	1884
616	" " " " "	no. 798	1885
617	" " " " "	no. 799	1885
618	" " " " "	no. 7100	1885-86
619	Polar Catalogue, Obsv. + Reductions,	no. 7101	1885
620	" " " " "	no. 7102	
621	Collection of Results in order of dates		beg. 1879-81
622	Readings of the Sun		1879
623	Observations of the Sun		1879
624	Error of Frodsham 1327, M.F. Michaels + W.W.W. ^{White}		1903-04
625	" " " M.F.M. + W.W.W.		1904-05
626	" " " M.F.M.		1905
627	" " " M.F.M.		1905-06
628	" " " JAD + Wh.		1906-07
629	" " " Wh.		1907-08
630	" " " Wh.		1908
631	Error of Frodsham Clock no. 1327, JAD		1901
632	" " " JAD		1899-1900
633	" " " JAD		1896-1898
634	" " " JAD + M.F.M.		1902-1903
635	Chronograph Record, WAR ^{W.A. Rogers}		1879-
636	Gen. " " AM ^{Augustus Me Connell} J3		1871
637	" " " AM + NC J4		1871
638	" " " WAR J5		1872
639	" " " WAR J6		1872- 3
640	" " " WAR J7		1872-73

KG 11366

641	Chronograph Record	WAR, J8	1873
642	"	" , WAR, J9	1873-74
643	"	" , WAR, J10	1874
644	"	" , WAR J11	1874-75
645	"	" WAR J12	1875
646	"	" WAR J13	1875-76
647	"	" WAR J14	1876
648	"	" WAR J15	1876
649	"	" WAR J16	1876-77
650	"	" WAR J17	1877
651	Chronograph Record	WAR J18	1877
652	"	" WAR J19	1878 (79)
653	"	" WAR J21	1879-1880
654	"	" WAR J22	1880
655	"	" WAR+WVB ^{W V Brown} J24	1880-81
656	"	" J25	1881
657	"	" WVB J26	1881
658	"	" WVB J27	1881-82
659	"	" WVB? J28	1883
660	"	" WVB? J29	1883
661	"	" ? J30	1883-84
662	Reports, Meteorological Notes		1889-94
663	"	" "	1886-1888
664	"	" "	1883-1885
665	North Pole Reductions		1897-1901
666	South Pole Reductions SP?		1896-1902
667	Variable Stars, Computations	T6	1895, 1897, 1901
668	Tabulations of Observations of Variable Stars,	T7	1903
669	Memoranda and Reminders	T9	1896?

KG 11366

670	Bright Double Stars, Working Lists		
671	Current Relative and Absolute Estimates ^{of variable stars}		1896-
672	Variable Stars, Computations		1899
673	Ephemerides of Variable Stars		1902
674	Clock Errors, Instrumental Constants, gen. Cat. A	WAR+AM	K1 1871-2
675	" " , Polar Catalogue, Instrumental Constants, HCO,		K2 1872-3
676	" " , Gen. Catalogue, " "		K3 1874-5
677	" " , Instrumental Constants,		K4 1878-9
678	" " " "		K5 1883
679	Equator Points, Corrections		K6 1871-73
680	Equator Pt. Corrections and Flexure, Polar Catalogue		K7 1872-73
681	Equator Pt. Corr. + Flexure Constants		K8 K9 1878
682	Equator Pt. from Observations of α + λ Ursae Minoris, WAR JFM		K10 1876
683	Copy of Instrumental Constants 1870-71. Redetermin. of $\Delta T + m + h'$		K11 K12 1870-78
684	Instrumental Constants depending on Pulkova Coordinates		K13 1871-72
685	" " " " " "		K14 1872-73
686	" " " " " "		K15 1873-74
687	" " " " " "		K16 1875
688	" " " " " "		K17 1876
689	" " " " " "		K18 1877
690	" " " " " "		K19 1877
691			
691	Final Values of $\Delta T + m$ + Req. for Reduction of Zone Observations		K20 1870-74
692	" " " " " " " " " "		K21 1874-1878
693	Final Values of the n and c		K22 1872-1876
694	" " " " " " 1870-72		K23 1876-78
695	Meridian Circle Constants, A , Star Constants, WAR		K26 1872
696	Instrumental Constants, Star Constants		K27 1876
697	Inclination of Declination Wires	JFU	K28 1877
698	D.M. Places for 1855 + 1875, Zone Observations, Final Reductions.	#J1	
699	" " " " " " " " " "	#J2	

KG 11366

700	DM Places for 1855.0 + 1875.0, Zone Observations, Final Reduction	#J 3	
701	DM " " " " " " " " " "	#J 4	
702	" " " " " " " " " "	#J 5	
703	DM " " " " " " " " " "	Supplement List #J 6	1883-8
704	D.M. List +53° +54° by Austin ?		1883
705	D.M. List +50° +51° +52°		
706	Thermometer, Barometer Runs,	#D 4	1873-
707	" " " "	#D 8	1875
708	" " " "	#D 9	1875-
709	" " " "	#D 10	1876
710	Planet + Satellite Observations	# R 14	
711	Star Observations	R 17	1877
712	" "	R 18	1877-78
713	" "	R 27	1869 and later
714	Meteorological Record	R 67	1880-82
715	Notes on S.M.P.	vol. 10	1892
716	micrometer Level	vol. 12	1877
717	Reduction of obsv by Schmidt by Reed	vol 17-	
718	Early Lists of Gas. Neb., Stars Pec. Spectra	vol. 33	1880
719	Discussion of H.A. 24, Group M.P. accord to DM	vol. 34	
720	" " " " " " " "	vol. 35	
		vol. 38	
721	Stars and Clusters, Lists with X Plates entered.	vol. 38 (by DJB)	1899
722	Double Stars		
723	" "		
724	Asteroid Zone Book		
725	Eros Book No. 3.		1893
726	" " " 4.		1876
727	Zone Stars		1870
728	Russian Transit	U 4	
729	Zone Circle Recordings	U 5	1870
730	" " " "	U 6	

KG 11366

731	Zone Circle Recordings	U7	1871
732	D-M List	U10	
733	Brown's Note Book	U	1880
734	Record of the work done by D. B. Pratt	U	1883-84
735	Stars (Zone) Needing reexamination of chronograph sheets	U14	1871
736	Stars to be reobserved	U15	
737	Star Places	U16	1875.0
738	K' K d.d' 3/1	U17	
739	" " 3	U18	
740	Zero Stars, Red. to appn't Place	U19	
741	Table for Reductions	U20	
742	Fundamental Stars, Ephemerides	U22	1879
743	Fundamental Stars, Ephemerides	U23	1879
744	Working Lists, Fundamental Stars	U24	1879
745	List of Fundamental Stars	U25	1879
746	Longitude Campaigne - Obs. + Red.	U27	1872-73
747	Miscellaneous Observations	U28	1881
748	Montreal Cambridge, Longitude Observations	U30	1883
749	Longitude Campaigne between Mont. + Cam.	U31	1883
750	Gen. Cat. List	U34	
		U37	
751	Bork WAR	U37	1875
MISSING	Chronograph Record	U38	
753	Chronograph Record	U40	1881
754	List of Polar Stars with dates of Obs.	U41	1885 1885
755	Flexure Collimations Runs W.C.		1880
756	Investigations of Circle Obs. Observations		1879 1879
757	Longitude of Circle Errors		1881
758	Investigation of Circle Discussion		
759	" of Errors of West Circle from Stops, for		1884
760	Investigation of Circle		1877-79

KG 11366

761	Investigation of Circle Observation		1871-79
762	Investigation of Errors of West Circle for Stops		1884-85
763	" " " " " " " "		1885
764	" " " " " " " "		1885
765	" " " " " " " "		1885
766	Invest. of Circle Observation		1879
767	Sup. Ed. & Var. Stars no. 3		1900
768	" " " " " no 4		1902
769	" " " " " no 6	by RWL	1894
770	" " " " " no. 9	by RWL 9	1903
771			
771	Various Stars	Zone P.M. XI	
772	" "	" " XII	
773	Arequipa Time Book No 1		1891-92
774	Chronograph Comparisons	by JAD + WW	1892.
775	Comparison of Waltham clock with South clock	by WAR	1878
776	Error of Sidereal Clock		by Wh, JAD 1908
777	" " " " "	Philip by Phillip Reilly	1913
778	" " " " "	by Phillip Reilly	1911
779	" " " " "	" " "	1910
780	Observations	by WAR	1876
781	Time Book	by WAR	1875
782	" "	by WAR	1874
783	" "	" "	1874
784	" "	" "	1874
785	Time Service [clock errors?]	" "	1879
786	Clock Errors	" "	1878
787	Time Service		1888-1890
788	Time Service	JAD	1890-1890
789	" "	Mr. Dunne	1891

KG 11366

790	Time Service + Russian Transit.	by L.W.	1877
791	Check Readings of Sheets of Obs. for Longitude.	Henry Gannett	1871
792	Russian Transit		188.
793	Time Service, Clock Errors & Russian Transit	L.W.	1877
794	" " " " " "	" "	"
795	" " , Clock Comparisons	Frank Waldo.	1881
796	Level of E. Transit	Leonard Waldo	1877
797	Time Service		1887-8
798	" "		1882-8
799	" " JAD.		1892-9;

800

KG 11366

800	Time Service	Miss Harriet Wace	1880
801	Clock Comparisons	<u>Time Service</u> Frank Waldo	1879 - 1880
802	Clock Comparisons	<u>Time Service</u> Leonora Waldo	1878 - 1879
803	<u>Reference Book</u> Stars, Asteroids, etc. observed or under observation		
804	Erratum in Rogers' AGC catalogue	JAD	1904
805	Meridian Circle General Record	W. A. Rogers	1879 - 80
806	Constellations		
807	Working List of Star Data		1871
808	Working List of Star Data for 1880		1880 - 81
809	Constellation Data		1879 - 80
810	Reduction of Bonn Observations from 1856 to 1875		
811	Discordant Stars		
812	Reports on the observation of the stars in the Northern Heavens up to the fifth magnitude		
813	Star Reduction	1890	Pulkova (Fundamental Stars) 1879
814	Measures of Plates		1890
815	Computations on Longitude and Latitude of Bolivian + Peruvian Stations No. 2 1894		
816	Zone Observations		1883 - 84
817	<u>Measurements</u> W. A. Rogers <u>Micrometer</u> No. 1		1894 - 97
818	Sun Images		1880
819	Miscellaneous Notes	Mr. Bond	
820	Chronograph Sheet Readings		1884
821	Computation of Residuals		
822	Corrections for Error		1869 - 70
823	Observations of Southern Variable Stars		1899 - 1904
824	Nautical Almanac		1883 1883-84
825	Lunar Brightness		1881
826	12 inch Horizontal Telescope XII Records		1899
827	Satellite <u>IV</u>		1888 - 90
828	Reductions		
829	Bibliography		

830	Observations and Reductions	Part II	1876
831	" " "	Part III	1876
832	Re-readings of Chronograph Sheets		1880
833	Investigation of Division Errors of Circle "East"		1880-81
834	Chronograph Readings	Miss H. Steven	1881
835	Readings of Chronograph Sheets	Leonard Waldo	1879
836	Star Data		1884-85
837	" "		1882
838	Star + Comet Data	Palmer C. Rickells	1881-84
839	Reductions	Sc Chandler Jr.	1880-81
			1881
840	Comet Data + Comparison Stars		1881
841	Time Service	WA Rogers	1885-86
842	Dates of Observations of Zone Stars for 1883 and 1884		
843	Miscellaneous Star Observations		
844	Star Observations		
845	Zone Observations		1884
846			
847			
848			
849			

4/30/1901 note in
New Campus

11366

846 ^{Fundamental} ~~Fundamental~~ + Zone Stars. Crile Neelys 2/19/85 - 6/1/85

847 Current Obs's of Var. Stars. - (J(?)2) 1895-96

848 Record of Obs's of F. W. Grover - 1898 * ~~1898~~ 6/19/99 - 9/1/01

849 H. C. Bailey Var. Star. Obs's. 1899 4/8/99 - 3/3/00

850 Absolute Work Pins 1879, 80, 81 (11/98) - 3/1/99 ~~1879~~ ¹⁸⁷⁹

851 (Var. Stars.) 11/28/83 - 12/28/84

852 Albat Dome 6 1/4" Olcese S.C.C. 4/27/83 - 9/26/83

853 10/4/83 - 11/27/83

854 11/13/96 - 1/5/98

855 Wedge Zones(?) - 11/1/87 - ?

856 Connection to Ephemeris (Jupiter's rate) _{table for weights} ?

857 Final adopted magn's for Comp. Stars for Var. (? - 5/29/01 - ?)

858 " " (c. 1900)

859 Var. + other stars - naked eye obs's. 4/26/89 - 3/20/90 ^{contains} photostv

860 Var. Star. Obs's H.C.B. ~~1894-95~~ 1894-95

861 Var. Stars. (#19) 12/13/88 - 9/7/99

862 ^{Computer} Book #18 10/4/99 - 00 - ?

863 " #17 c. 4/02

864 Wedge Photometer Zone Stars 10/23/94 - ?

865 Meridian Photometry. 9/1/81 3/18/84
list of Stars in Heis' Catalog ~~1894~~ (See Catalogue ?)

25

(notes on slide?) in draft?

866 Multiplet Theory (H.N. Russell) 1925, obs.; Nova theory.

867 P.H.s to be examined in context w/ Dr. Peters' "Connections of ¹⁸⁷⁷⁻⁷⁸ Her. Zones"

868 Equatorial Zones 1877 (R21) also Sophocles, (Anst. 1877) ^{Burfield}

869 Loc. of Comp Stars for Ver's. c. 3/7/94

870 (pp. 21-112, 237-253) ^{Comm} Flint ~~Bl~~-Opt. Data c. 7/7/02-1/03
note (3/29/16) @ paint.

871 HCO Chronograph Record 1870 (6/22 - 11/1) (J1)

872 " " " 7/12/70 - 6/12/71 (J2)

873 Psychrometer Comparisons (Anguilla + other stations) ⁹⁶⁻ c. 1877 R.D. Wend

874 Mexic. Notes (packages, ~~work plans~~) 1862-1869

875 (also 11365.778) Ver. Star Obs's 1901 - Len Campbell 2/26 - 8/4
Vol. 2, No. 2

876 Readings of Thermometers G₁ + G₂, U. Br + Standard Heat Meter from 1/30 - 4/19
(P5)

1072 (over)

1073

1074

1075

1076

1077

~~1078~~
~~1079~~
~~1080~~
~~1081~~

also
Planet Photometry; Conj. of Jupiter + Saturn (12/30/78)

new
data
sheets

KG 11366.

~~870~~

872

873

874

875

876

877

878

879

880

881

882

883

884

885

886

887

888

889

890

891

892

893

894

895

896

897

898

899

900

See later sheets

HLP

T

~~2~~
~~3~~
~~4~~

5

6

7

8

9

10

11

12

13

15

14

16

17

18

19

20

21

22

23

24

KG 1366.

HLP

900		25
902		26
903		27
904		28
905		29
906		30
907		31
908		32
909		33
910		34
911		35
912		36
913		37
914		38
915		39
916		40
917		41
918		42
919		43
920		44
921		45
922		46
923		47
924		48
925		49
926		50
927		51
928		52
929		53
930		54

V

K 6 11366,

UCLP

931		55
932		56
933		57
934		58
935		59
936		60
937		61
938		62
939		63
940		64

941		65
942		65
943		66
944		67
945		68
946		69
947		70
948		71
949		72
950		73

951		74
952		75
953		76
954		77
955		78
956		79
957		80
958		81
959		82
960		83

KG. 11368.

HLP

961		84
962		85
963		86
964		87
965		88
966		89
967		90
968		115
969		116
970		117
971		118
972		119
973		120
974		121
975		122
976		123
977		124
978		125
979		126
980		127
981		128
982		129
983		130
984		131
985		132
986		133
987		134
988		135
989		137
990		138

KG 11366.

H.L.P.

991		139
992		140
993		141
994		142
995		143
996		144
997		145
998		146
999		147
1000		148
1001		149
1002		150
1003		151
1004		152
1005		153
1006		154
1007		155
1008		156
1009		157
1010		158
1011		159
1012		160
1013		161
1014		162
1015		163
1016		164
1017		165
1018		166
1019		167
1020		168

KG 11366.

H. L. P

1021

169

1022

170

1023

171

1024

172

1025

173

1026

174

1027

175

1028

176

1029

177

1030

178

1031

179

1032

180

1033

181

1034

182

1035

184

1036

185

1037

186

1038

187

1039

188

1040

189

1041

190

1042

191

1043

v. 192

1044

1045

1046

1047

1048

1049

1050

Rep. plates
Rep. plates

KG 11366.

1051	H. human Plates (Suspected SH Leland 20406)	—
1052	"	—
1053	(Neptune Plates)	—
1054	"	—
1055	(Suppl. Mats + Data)	—
1056	(Horn's Connection)	—
1057	"	—
1058	(Neptune Plates)	—
1059	(Supplementary Mats)	—
1060	"	—
1061	"	—
1062	"	—
1063	"	—
1064	"	—
1065	"	—
1066	"	—
1067	"	—
1068	"	—
		<u>V</u> 136

~~1069~~

~~1070~~

1068
876
—
192

HARVARD COLLEGE OBSERVATORY
ARCHIVES

CATALOGUE NOTES:

KG 11366.874 to KG 11366.1068

[195 Volumes]

3/27/73 - 3/30/73

J. Tinsch

Cases III - ~~IV~~ V 376E

Cases I - IV 377W

KG 11366.874

4 3/4" x 8"

(90 pages)

4 p. accounts { (i) Almanac for 1862 (mom)
with rates { (ii) Mon for 1864 Lunar Ephemeris + Lunar Distances

1 p. 1 Prod of Curv. of Ellipse.

5th Ephemeris

1 p. 1869 Delin. : Distances, Books, Table. Jan 26
Desk, Jan. 19

3 p. [notes from Naval Academy, by Sir Howard Douglas
" " Naval College (?)]

mostly blank notebook

873
+ 195
1068

COVER SHEET

3/27/73 - 3/30/73

~~41~~
~~42~~
~~43~~
~~44~~
~~45~~
~~46~~
~~47~~
~~48~~
~~49~~
~~50~~
x 150

Shelf IV .1071 - .1075

Shelf V .1076 - .1081

Shelf VI empty

~~Draw~~

KG 11366.874

Item: Notebook: $4\frac{3}{4}'' \times 8\frac{1}{4}''$
90 pages

- Contents: ① estimates of time + work ^{→ des. of labor} for production of
lunar and stellar ephemerides, © 1862, 1864
② Computations of rad. of curv. of ellipse
③ Palimpsest: Instruments, Desk and Books (Jan. 19, 1869)
and Table (Jan. 26, 1869)
④ Notes from Naval Academy, by Sir Howard Douglas
+ (?) Naval College.

Notes: Unidentified author; 10 pages of writing

Date: 1862 - 1869?

KG 11366.875 also 11365.778

Item: Notebook: $3\frac{7}{8}'' \times 6\frac{3}{4}''$ 186 pages.
"Variable Star Observations" } Vol. 2, No. 2
Feb. 20, 1901 - Aug. 4, 1901 "
Leon Campbell

178⁺² pages of writing

* Del. list

Also: KG ~~11365.776~~ and KG 11365.778

KG 11366.876

Item: Notebook: 5" x 7 7/8" 96 pages.

G₁, G₂ re thermometers

Eds: "P5"

"Reductions of Thermometers G₁
G₂ U. Bar + Standard Half Meter

from Jan 30 to Apr. 19 (year not given)"

Standard for
T, P + L.

KG 11366.877

Notebook: 7 1/8" x 8 3/8"

" I : 863, 872, 873"

Eds: "General lunar plate measurements + reductions"
Mary Fowler
T(?)

Sept., 1912 ~~to~~

Sept 20, 1912 - Dec. 2, 1912

Plate 863 1/12/11

872 1/16/11

873 1/11/11

KG 11366.878

II : 864, 865, 878, 879
1/15/11 1/15/11 1/17/11 1/17/11

"Measurements +
Reductions"

Oct 2 - Dec 3, 1912

KG 11366.879

III 920 921 922

932

2/15/11 →

2/18/11

Oct. 14, 1912 - Apr. 10, 1913

KG 11366.880

IV 933 934 936
2/18/11 2/18/11 3/9/11

967

Oct. 23 - Apr. 7

KG 11366.881

V : 968 972 974 977
3/9/11 3/11/11 3/11/11 3/13/11

Oct. 30 - Apr. 14

.882 VI 978 979 1028 1029
3/13/11 3/13/11 4/10/11 4/10/11

Nov. 15 - Apr. 12

.883 VII 1030 1034 1035 1049
4/10/11 4/11/11 4/11/11 4/16/11

Nov. 26 - Feb. 10

.884 VIII 1050 1051 1067 1068 1069
4/16/11 5/3/11

Dec. 2 - Apr. 11

.885 IX 1041 1042 1043 1078 1079
4/12/11 5/4/11

Dec. 10 - Apr. 28

.886 X 1080 1085 1086 1122 1092
5/4/11 5/5/11 6/3/11 5/6/11

Jan. 1, 1913 - Apr. 28

.887 XI 1093 1094 1123 1124 1125
5/6/11 6/3/11 6/7/11

Jan. 7 - Apr. 26

7 "x 8 1/8"

.888 XII 1126 1128 Jan 18 - Feb 25, 1913
6/7/11 6/8/11

.889 XIII 1129 1130 Jan. 22 - Feb. 17
6/8/11 6/8/11

.890 XIV } note 1301 1302 1303 Feb 25 - Apr. 17 (May 14?)
10/7/11

.891 XV 1166 1257 Jan. 28, 1913 - Jan. 31, 1914(?)
7/7/11 9/10/11

.892 XVI 1304 1305 March 1, May 12, 1913
10/7/11

.893 XVII 1307 1308 1309 March 5 - May 13
10/7/11

.894 XVIII 1310 1311 1312 March 12 May 14
10/7/11

.895 XIX 1313 1314 1315 March 21 - May 14
10/7/11

.896 ~~XX~~ 1318 1319 1331 March 21 - May 27
"painted the obs." stamped inside
10/9/11 10/9/11 10/13/11

.897 XXI 1168 Apr. 22, 1913
7/7/11

.898 XXII 1332 1375 1376 May 26 - 31
10/13/11 11/2/11 11/2/11

.899 XXIII 1380 1381 1397 May 29 - July 2
p40 11/3/11 ? 11/5/11

.900 XXIV 1398 1402 1403 June 2 - July 8
11/5/11 11/7/11

.901 XXV 1407 1408 1412 June 13 - 18
11/12/11 11/13/11

.902 XXVI 1413 1446 1445 June 17 - 30
11/13/11 11/29/11

.903 XXVII 1452 1453 1462 June 21 - Sept 30
12/2/11 12/4/11

.904 XXVIII 1463 1518 1519 June 24 - Sept. 26
12/4/11 12/30/11

.905 XXIX 1520 1521 1524 June 28 - Sept. 26
1/1/12 1/3/12

.906 XXX 1525 1542 1543 July 3 - Sept. 29
1/3/12 1/9/12

.907 XXXI 1549 1550 1590 July 10 - Sept. 30
1/10/12 1/27/12

.908 XXXII 1591 ~~1598~~ 1598 July 19 - Sept. 29
1/27/12 1/31/12

.909 XXXIII 1599 1606 Sept. 18 - Sept. 30
1/31/12 2/6/12

M. Fowler, 14 Prospect Street (in case 4.914)

- .910 XXXIV 1607 1662 1668 Sept 22 - Oct. 2
2/6/12 2/23/12 2/23/12
- .911 XXXV 1669 1674 1675 Oct. 3 - Oct. 6, 1913
2/27/12 2/28/12
- .912 XXXVI 1682 1683 1696 Oct. 7 - Oct. 9
2/24/12 3/2/12
- .913 XXXVII 1697 1702 1703 Oct. 10 - 14
3/2/12 3/5/12
- .914 XXXVIII 1737 1739 1743 Oct. 15 - 17
3/25/12 3/27/12
- .915 XXXIX 1744 1742 Oct. 20, 1913
3/27/12 3/29/12
- .916 XL 1749 1750 1751 Oct. 23 - 25
3/29/12 3/30/12
- .917 XL I 1759 1760 1790 Oct. 27 - 28
4/3/12 4/25/12
- .918 XL II 1791 1795 Oct. 30 - 31
4/25/12 4/27/12
- .919 XL III 1796 1801 1802 Nov. 4 - 6
4/27/12 4/30/12
- .920 XL IV 1808 1809 1826 Nov. 7 - 10
5/2/12 5/25/12
- .921 XL V 1827 1884 Nov. 11 - 13
5/27/12 7/2/12

.922 XLVI 1885 1889 1890 Nov. 15 - Nov. 18
7/2/12 7/3/12 1913

.923 XLVII 1930 1931 1956 Nov. 24 - Nov. 26
8/5/12 8/27/12

.924 XLVIII 1957 1963 1964 Nov. 28 - Dec. 2
8/27/12 8/29/12

.925 XLIX 1973 1974 Dec. 3 - Dec. 4
8/30/12

.926 L 1980 1981 2009 Dec. 5 - Dec. 6
8/31/12 9/25/12

.927 LI 2010 2011 2012 Dec. 8 - 12
9/25/12 9/27/12

.928 LII 2014 2015 2074 Dec. 13 - 17
9/29/12 10/21/12

.929 LIII 2076 2081 2082 Dec. 18 - 22
10/21/12 10/30/12

.930 LIV 2093 2094 2145 Dec. 23 - Jan. 6, 1914
11/2/12 11/18/12

.931 LV 2146 2172 Jan. 8
11/18/12 11/20/12

.932 LVI 2173 2180 2181 Jan. 12 - 15
11/20/12 11/21/12

.933 LVII 2184 2185 2234 Jan. 16 - 19
11/25/12 11/30/12

.934 LVIII 2235 2367 2368 Jan. 20 - 23
11/30/12 12/19/12

.935 LIX 2374 2375 2377 Jan. 26 - 29
12/20/12 12/24/12

.936 LX 2378 2386 2387 Feb. 2 - 5
12/24/12 1/25/12

.937 LXI 2493 2494 2782 Feb. 9 - Feb. 11
1/22/13 2/15/13

.938 LXII 2783 2797 2798 Feb. 16 - 19
2/15/13 2/18/13

.939 LXIII 2371 2182 2368 (Veneceves) Feb. 20 - March 4
12/19/12 11/2/12 (12/19/12)

.940 LXIV 2992 2994 3008 March 5 - 19 + ? date(s)
3/17/13 3/18/13

.941 LXV 3010 3023 3024 March 21 - 25
3/18/13 3/19/13

.942 LXVI 1698 1748 March 9 - 10
3/2/12 3/29/12

.943 LXVI 2751 2752 Apr. 1 - 2
2/14/13

.944 LXVII 3045 3046 3189 Apr. 6 - 8
3/22/13 4/17/13

.945 LXVIII 3215 3376 Apr. 13 - 14
4/19/13 5/12/13

.874 - .944 on shelf I of Case IV of 377W

.945 - .1020 on shelf II "

.946 L XIX 3377 3385 3387 Apr. 23 - May 1
5/12/13 5/14/13 5/14/13

.947 LXX 3485 3486 3535 Apr. 30 - May 5
6/13/13 7/22/13

.948 LXXI 3536 3601 May 7
7/22/13 8/12/13

.949 LXXII 3648 3649 May 8
8/19/13

.950 LXXIII 3669 3783 May 9 - (?)
8/20/13 9/10/13

.951 LXXIV 3784 3811 (?) - May 14
9/10/13 9/13/13

.952 LXXV 3812 3844 May 15 - (?)
9/13/13 9/14/13

.953 LXXVI 3846 3856 (?) - May 25
9/14/13 9/15/13

.954 LXXVII 3857 4096 May 26 - 27
9/15/13 10/21/13

.955 LXXVIII 4097 4239 May 28 - 29
10/21/13 11/6/13

.956 LXXIX 4271 4272 Oct. 24, 1914 - Jan. 6, 1915
11/7/13 11/7/13

.957 LXXX 4295 4296 Jan. 7 - Feb. 3, 1915
11/12/13

.958 LXXXI 4297 4298 Feb 5-15
11/13/13

.959 LXXXII 4303 4304 4309 Feb 17-23
11/14/13

.960 LXXXIII 4336 4374 4375 Feb. 25 - Mar 3
11/20/13 11/22/13

.961 LXXXIV 4423 4424 4455 Mar 6-15
12/8/13 12/11/13

.962 LXXXV 4456 4465 4466 March 17-22
12/11/13 12/13/13

.963 LXXXVI 4478 4481 Mar 24-
12/13/13 12/14/13

.964 LXXXVII 4503 4554 4555 March 26 - Apr. 23
12/18/13 1/5/14 1/5/14

.965 LXXXVIII 4571 4572 4588 Apr. 27 - 29
1/6/14 1/10/14

.966 LXXXIX 4589 4619 4620 May 4-6
1/10/14 1/17/14

.967 ~~LXXX~~ XC 4677 4678 4690 May 7 - 11, 1915
2/2/14 2/4/14
"M. Fowler P. U. Obs., Pinet" (on cover)

Miss Fowler

Martha C Barton (?)
BOSTON

change of address

- ✓ .968 CXV 7549 7571 7572 ?
1/7/15 1/8/15
- .969 CXVI 7665 7666, 7677 Jan 22, 1916 - Jan 31
1/20/15 1/26/15
- .970 CXVII 7678 7692 7693 Feb 2 - 5
1/26/15 1/29/15
- .971 CXVIII 7965 7966 7990 Apr. 24, 1916 - ^{Apr.} 26
2/20/15 2/25/15
- .972 CXIX 8013 8014 8052 May 4 - 20
2/27/15 3/2/15
- ✓ .973 CXX 8110 8288 8289 (?)
3/4/15 3/23/15
- ✓ .974 CXXI 8299 8300 8306 (?)
3/24/15 3/26/15
- ✓ .975 CXXII 8307 8316 8317 (?)
3/26/15 3/27/15
- ✓ .976 CXXIII 8346 8347 8362 May 22, 1916 - May 26
3/30/15 4/4/15
- .977 CXXIV 8635 8636 8639 May 30 - June 7
5/29/15 5/30/15
- .978 CXXV 8640 8904 8905 June 8 - 12
5/30/15 7/27/15

✓ BORTON

Ernestine Fuller

✓ .979 CXXVI 8649 8650 8690 (?)
5/31/15 6/23/15

✓ ~~.979~~ .980 CXXVII 8728 8729 (?)
6/28/15

✓ .981 CXXVIII 8726 8727 8731 (?)
6/28/15 6/29/15

✓ .982 CXXIX 8732 8890 8891 (?)
6/29/15 7/24/15

✓ .983 CXXX 9079 9080 9086 (?)
8/25/15 8/26/15

✓ .984 CXXXI 9087 9193 9194 ~~Sept.~~ Sept. 18, 1916
8/26/15 9/18/15 9/21/15

✓ .985 CXXXII 9195 9249 9250 Sept. 1916
9/21/15 9/23/15

✓ .986 CXXXIII 9263 9264 9286 Sept. 1916
9/27/15 9/28/15

✓ .987 CXXXIV 9377 9378 9388 (?)
10/16/15 10/21/15

✓ .988 CXXXV 9389 9413 9414 (?)
10/21/15 10/23/15

* Note See .1068 for missing volume
✓ ~~.988~~ .989 CXXXVII 9461 9492 9491 (?)
10/27/15 10/30/15

* Genevieve Fuller

✓ .990 CXXXVIII 9495 9496 9732 (?)
 11/1/15 11/13/15

✓ .991 CXXXIX 9733 9754 9782 (?)
 11/17/15 11/18/15 11/22/15

✓ .992 CXL 9783 9785 9786 (?)
 11/22/15 11/24/15

✓ .993 CXLI 9817 9818 9859 ~~(?)~~ (1916)
 11/26/15 11/30/15

✓ .994 CXLII 9860 9997 9998 (1916)
 11/30/15 12/15/15

* .995 CXLIII 10030 10031 10072 (?)
 12/16/15 12/21/15

* .996 CXLIV 10073 10103 (?)
 12/21/15 12/22/15

✓ .997 CXLV 10227 10228 10231 (?)
 1/14/16 1/17/16

10102 is blank + shows format

✓ .998 CXLVI 10232 10263 10264 (?)
 1/17/16 1/18/16

* .999 CXLVII 10385 10386 10532 (?)
 2/15/16 3/11/16

* .1000 CXLVIII 10533 10604 10760 (?)
 3/11/16 3/23/16 5/20/16

- ✓ .1001 CXLIX 10692 10693 10701 (?)
4/10/16 4/13/16
- ✓ .1002 ~~CL~~ CL 10702 10716 10718 (?) (1917??)
4/13/16 4/15/16
- ✓ .1003 CLI 10737 10738 10743 (?)
5/11/16 5/12/16
- ✓ .1004 CLII 10746 10748 10753 (?)
5/13/16 5/17/16
- * .1005 CLIII 10761 10933 10934 (?)
5/20/16 7/14/16
- * .1006 CLIV 10605 10998 10999 (?)
3/23/16 8/12/16
- ✓ .1007 CLV 11004 11006 11039 (?)
8/13/16 8/15/16
- ✓ .1008 CLVI 11160 ~~11161~~ 11197 (?)
9/11/16 9/16/16
← incomplete
- ✓ .1009 CLVII 11198 11201 11202 (?)
9/16/16 9/17/16
- * .1010 CLVIII 11208 11209 11218 (?)
9/19/16 9/20/16

?*
~~1011~~ CLIX 11219 11276 11285 (?)
9/20/16 10/9/16 10/10/16

?*
~~1012~~ CLX 11286 11301 11302 (?)
10/10/16 10/11/16

✓ 1013 CLXI 11314 11315 11522 (?)
10/12/16 11/3/16

✓ 1014 CLXII 11331 11336 11337 (?)
10/14/16 10/17/16

✓ 1015 CLXIII 11523 11542 11544 (?)
11/3/16 11/6/16

✓ 1016 CLXIV 11549 11550 11580 (?)
11/7/16 11/8/16

✓ 1017 CLXV 11581 11597 11598 (?)
11/8/16 11/10/16

?* 1018 CLXVI 11636 11708 11709 (?)
11/11/16 11/18/16

?* 1019 CLXVII 11870 11871 11890 (?)
12/6/16 12/7/16

?* 1020 CLXVIII 11891 11909 11910 (?)
12/7/16 12/8/16

End of Shelf II

Shelf III .1021 - .10~~24~~₇₀

✓ .1021 CLXIX $\underbrace{11924 \quad 11925}_{12/10/16}$ 11931 (?)
12/12/16

✓ .1022 CLXX $\times 11932$ $\underbrace{\times 11997 \quad \times 11998}_{12/29/16}$ (?)
12/12/16

?* ~~✓~~ .1023 CLXXI $\underbrace{12017 \quad 12018}_{1/2/17}$ 12027 (?)
1/6/17

?* .1024 CLXXII 12028 $\underbrace{12043 \quad 12044}_{1/11/17}$ (?)
1/6/17

✓ .1025 CLXXIII $\underbrace{12068 \quad 12069}_{1/12/17}$ 12075 (?)
1/14/17

✓ .1026 CLXXIV 12076 $\underbrace{12266 \quad 12267}_{12/30/17}$ (?)
1/14/17

✓ .1027 CLXXV $\underbrace{12280 \quad 12281}_{2/1/17}$ 12296 (?)
2/3/17

?* ~~✓~~ .1028 CLXXVI $\underbrace{12301 \quad 12300}_{2/5/17}$ 12297 (?)
2/3/17

?* .1029 CLXXVII $\underbrace{12323 \quad 12324}_{2/6/17}$ 12469 (?)
3/6/17

?* .1030 CLXXVIII 12470 $\underbrace{12474 \quad 12475}_{3/8/17}$ (?)
3/6/17

?* .1031 CLXXIX $\frac{12507 - 12508}{3/12/17}$ 12525 $\frac{3/13/17}{(?)}$

?* .1032 CLXXX 12526 $\frac{12723 \quad 12724}{3/30/17}$ $\frac{3/13/17}{(?)}$

?* .1033 CLXXXI $\frac{12740 \quad 12741}{4/3/17}$ 12774 $\frac{4/4/17}{(?)}$

?* .1034 CLXXXII 12775 $\frac{13018 \quad 13019}{7/7/17}$ $\frac{4/4/17}{(?)}$

NOTE

?* .1035 CLXXXIV 13085 $\frac{13274 \quad 13273}{8/27/17}$ $\frac{8/3/17}{(?)}$

✓ .1036 CLXXXV $\frac{13109 \quad 13110}{8/4/17}$ 13124 $\frac{8/5/17}{(?)}$

✓ .1037 CLXXXVI 13125 $\frac{13143 \quad 13145}{8/7/17}$ $\frac{8/5/17}{(?)}$

?* .1038 CLXXXVII $\frac{13284 \quad 13285}{8/31/17}$ 13307 $\frac{9/4/17}{(?)}$

?* .1039 CLXXXVIII 13308 $\frac{13329 \quad 13330}{9/6/17}$ $\frac{9/4/17}{(?)}$

✓ .1040 CLXXXIX $\frac{13609 \quad 13611}{9/25/17}$ 13626 $\frac{9/30/17}{(?)}$

(+ change in cover marking.)

✓ .1041 CXC 13627 ~~9/30/17~~ 9/30/17 13641 13642 10/1/17 (?)

?* ~~.1042~~ CXC I 13668 13669 13716 10/2/17 10/6/17 (?)

✓ .1043 CXC II 13610 13645 13646 9/25/17 10/1/17 (?)

?* .1044 (193) 13717 13935 13936 10/6/17 10/30/17 (?)

✓ .1045 (194) 13621 13622 13140 9/30/17 8/7/17 (?)

✓† .1046 (195) 13142 8/7/17 (?)

?*† .1047 (196) 13331 13332 13305 9/6/17 9/11/17 (?)

? .1048 ~~(197)~~ 12017 - 14455 ^{OF PLATES} → [Jan ~~21~~²² 1917 - Dec 26] (?)

Plate Characteristics	Plate No.	Date	$\Delta\alpha$	$\Delta\delta$	$\mu\alpha$	$\mu\delta$			
			$\Delta T = \frac{\Delta\alpha}{\mu\alpha}$	$\mu\delta\Delta T$	o-c	R.A.	Rec.		
	also	RA	Rec	ΔR	D	a	e	b/d/a-e	Curvature, Dirty, etc.

PUO insert

? .1049

"Neptune Plates"

7099 - 11/28/14

7534 - 1/7/15

~~Dec 18/15~~ Jan. 15, 1915

Apr. 13, 1915

* .1050

"Neptune"

letter in care to Russell at PUO Dated 6/17/17
from EC P. Day Postmarked 6/29/17

saying Fisher Day + deserial of 5 Neptune plates

MC 11995
12010
12104
12270
12504

Reminded
3/30/73
JAT

w/ copy of letter from HN R to ECP Dated 7/3/17
mentioning Miss Fuller.

11995 → Dec 28, 1916 notes of Fuller + Russell

12010 ✓
Dec. 30, 1916

(inside cover)

.1051

"Measures of the Suspected Star halowide 20406" March 19, 1913

[Fowler]

Plate MC 1412 11/13/11

1413 11/13/11

1092 5/6/11

1093 5/6/11

1094 5/6/11

[↓ also ↓]

?

Remembrance + the computation of MC 2181 6/5/14

Fowler

.1052

4296

4295

Plate
reductions.
(dates?)

11/2/14 -

Notebooks: (loose) 7" x 8 3/8"

? HNR .1053 "Neptune Plates" 2/11/11 - 5/3/11
(P.U. exam book inst) Plate Reductions

②

- MC 689
 - 786
 - 804
 - 820
 - 809
 - 810
- } ? ~1911

HNR ① .1054 "Measurement + Reduction of Harvard Line Plates" 11/14/10 - 1/31/11
Henry Norris Russell Nov/1910

- MC 650, 651
 - 762, 763
 - 759, 760
 - 761, 877
- } ~1910

? .1055 "Supplementary Notes + Dates" ~
Corrections made to plates up to June 13, 1913 due to change in assumed values for irradiation
Plate 863 (1/12/11) → 3486 (4/13/13)

.1056 "Hayn's Correction for plates of Oct. 7, 1911" (?)
1301 - 1305 Computations of Earth Selenographic Coordinates
1307 - 1315

?# .1057 — 13306 12319 12320 (?)
9/4/17 2/6/17

Fowler .1058 "Neptune Plates" 4/14/15 - 4/20/15
7569 1/8/15
7597 1/9/15
7627 1/10/15
7651 1/13/15

.1059 "Supplementary Notes"
 Plates 3535 - 11998"
 (7/22/13 - 12/29/16)
 [similar to .1048]
 Fowler
 Fuller
 Bryan

* .1060 — 14455 12/26/17 (?)

* .1061 — 14448 14449 14454 (?)
 12/22/17 12/26/17

* .1062 — 14408 14416 14417 (?)
 11/28/17 12/2/17

* .1063 — 14399 14400 14407 (?)
 11/26/17 11/28/17

* .1064 — 14095 14131 14132 (?)
 11/4/17 11/5/17

* .1065 — 14045 14046 14094 (?)
 11/3/17 11/4/17

* .1066 — 13959 14027 14028 (?)
 10/31/17 11/2/17

* .1067 — 13914 13915 13958 (?)
 10/28/17 10/31/17

* .1068 CXXXVI
ADD 9421 9422 9460 (?)
 10/24/15 10/27/15

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK I.

MARY FOWLER

September 20, 1912 - December 2, 1912

Plate 863 (January 12, 1911)

Plate 872 (January 16, 1911)

Plate 873 (January 11, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK II.

MARY FOWLER

October 2, 1912 - December 3, 1912

Plate 864 (January 15, 1911)

Plate 865 (January 15, 1911)

Plate 878 (January 17, 1911)

Plate 879 (January 17, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK III.

MARY FOWLER

October 14, 1912 - April 10, 1913

Plate 920 (February 15, 1911)

Plate 921 (February 15, 1911)

Plate 922 (February 15, 1911)

Plate 932 (February 18, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK IV.

MARY FOWLER

October 23, 1912 - April 7, 1913

Plate 933 (February 18, 1911)

Plate 934 (February 18, 1911)

Plate 966 (March 9, 1911)

Plate 967 (March 9, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK V.

MARY FOWLER

October 30, 1912 - April 14, 1913

Plate 968 (March 9, 1911)

Plate 972 (March 11, 1911)

Plate 974 (March 11, 1911)

Plate 977 (March 13, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK VI.

MARY FOWLER

November 15, 1912 - April 12, 1913

Plate 978 (March 13, 1911)

Plate 979 (March 13, 1911)

Plate 1028 (April 10, 1911)

Plate 1029 (April 10, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK VII.

MARY FOWLER

November 26, 1912 - February 10, 1913

Plate 1030 (April 10, 1911)

Plate 1034 (April 11, 1911)

Plate 1035 (April 11, 1911)

Plate 1049 (April 16, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK VIII.

MARY FOWLER

December 2, 1912 - April 11, 1913

Plate 1050 (April 16, 1911)

Plate 1051 (April 16, 1911)

Plate 1067 (May 3, 1911)

Plate 1068 (May 3, 1911)

Plate 1069 (May 3, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK IX.

MARY FOWLER

December 10, 1912 - April 28, 1913

Plate 1041 (April 12, 1911)

Plate 1042 (April 12, 1911)

Plate 1043 (April 12, 1911)

Plate 1078 (May 4, 1911)

Plate 1079 (May 4, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK X.

MARY FOWLER

January 1, 1913 - April 28, 1913

Plate 1080 (May 4, 1911)

Plate 1085 (May 5, 1911)

Plate 1086 (May 5, 1911)

Plate 1122 (June 3, 1911)

Plate 1092 (May 6, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK XI.

MARY FOWLER

January 7, 1913 - April 26, 1913

Plate 1093 (May 6, 1911)

Plate 1094 (May 6, 1911)

Plate 1123 (June 3, 1911)

Plate 1124 (June 7, 1911)

Plate 1125 (June 7, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK XII.

MARY FOWLER

January 18, 1913 - February 25, 1913

Plate 1126 (June 7, 1911)

Plate 1128 (June 8, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK XIII.

MARY FOWLER

January 22, 1913 - February 17, 1913

Plate 1129 (June 8, 1911)

Plate 1130 (June 8, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK XV.

MARY FOWLER

February 25, 1913 - April 17, 1913 (May 14, 1913?)

Plate 1301 (October 7, 1911)

Plate 1302 (October 7, 1911)

Plate 1303 (October 7, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK XIV.

MARY FOWLER

January 28, 1913 - January 31, 1914 (1913?)

Plate 1166 (July 7, 1911)

Plate 1257 (September 10, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK XVI.

MARY FOWLER

March 1, 1913 - May 12, 1913

Plate 1304 (October 7, 1911)

Plate 1305 (October 7, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK XVII.

MARY FOWLER

March 5, 1913 - May 13, 1913

Plate 1307 (October 7, 1911)

Plate 1308 (October 7, 1911)

Plate 1309 (October 7, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK XVIII.

MARY FOWLER

March 12, 1913 - May 14, 1913

Plate 1310 (October 7, 1911)

Plate 1311 (October 7, 1911)

Plate 1312 (October 7, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK XIX.

MARY FOWLER

March 21, 1913 - May 14, 1913

Plate 1313 (October 7, 1911)

Plate 1314 (October 7, 1911)

Plate 1315 (October 7, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK XX.

MARY FOWLER

March 21, 1913 - May 27, 1913

Plate 1318 (October 9, 1911)

Plate 1319 (October 9, 1911)

Plate 1331 (October 13, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK XXI.

MARY FOWLER

April 22, 1913

Plate 1168 (July 7, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK XXII.

MARY FOWLER

May 26, 1913 - May 31, 1913

Plate 1332 (October 13, 1911)

Plate 1375 (November 2, 1911)

Plate 1376 (November 2, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK XXIII.

MARY FOWLER

May 29, 1913 - July 2, 1913

Plate 1380 (November 3, 1911)

Plate 1381 (November 3, 1911) (?)

Plate 1397 (November 5, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK XXIV.

MARY FOWLER

June 2, 1913 - July 8, 1913

Plate 1398 (November 5, 1911)

Plate 1402 (November 7, 1911)

Plate 1403 (November 7, 1911)

HARVARD LUNAR PLATES, MEASUREMENTS AND REDUCTIONS

NOTEBOOK XXV.

MARY FOWLER

June 13, 1913 - June 18, 1913

Plate 1407 (November 12, 1911)

Plate 1408 (November 12, 1911)

Plate 1412 (November 13, 1911)

KG

11366

1069

Fireballs-general

Index to Fireballs etc. (4 x 6 cds)

1900 formula

Note for Mr. Watson from William J. Fisher

Newcomb's Globe Method for Meteor Paths, 1867, 10 pages.

1900 Formula, 9 pages.

3 pages of handwritten calculations

Computation of bright meteor paths by the Newton-Denning Method with celestial globe, 6 pages. Note for Dr. Shapby from William J. Fisher, 1932 Dec. 19.

Computations, problems, Hoffmeister's formula for sea height, in Hevelius.

The gathering and reduction of fireball data. 1927, 5 p.

Computations, problems, etc. Meteors - Formulas for height computing 1931-1933, 4 pages

Reducing Fireball Observations, Feb. 12, 1926 5 pages.

Meteor Heights 1926, March 7. 1 page

Meteor Heights - Weighting observations, Hoffmeister theory and notations. 1 page

Inclination of Path and Earthpoint, 1926 Feb 25. 1 page

Inclination of a Meteor Path as seen from different azimuths, 1926 Feb. 21. 1 page

Merton's Method for comet places, etc. 1 page

Sun bearings of Meteor landmarks 1926 July 22 1 page

Meteor tracks - globe method

① H. A. Newton, Am. Journ. Sci. (2) 47, p. 399-413, 1869 } 3 pages
Meteors of Nov. 14, 1868. with plates I, II

② W. F. Denning, Telescopic Work for Starlight Evenings, London, 1891. p. 278-279 [Globe method for doubly observed meteors.] 2 pages

k G
11366
1069

Meteor Motion

- A rough theory of the relation between velocity and air density along the luminous paths of meteorites. Nov 16, 1933 ^{1 page}
- Table of data based on Schiaparelli's method. Nov 15, 1933 ^{1 page}
- Heights of shower meteors Denning 1913 1932 Feb. 24
- English observations. 1 page
- Data bearing on air penetration of meteorite. 1930 Nov. 16
- Computation, etc. 1931 6 pages
- Theory of the "gas cap" 1930 Apr. 16
- According to E. Mach, Pop. Sci. 1933 Nov. 16
- Lectures, p. 309-337 (Chicago, 1898) ~~on~~ treating the photographed wave in the front of a high speed bullet: ^{1 page} 2 pages
- Meteor head wave computations. 1930 Apr. 25 ^{1 page} checked anew and against old computation.
- Relative motion of meteor and earth 1930 Mar. 16
- Moulton shows that the relative velocity of a meteor with regard to earth (extra-atmospheric) cannot be less than 7 mi/sec., nearly. Computation. 2 pages.
- Motion of a Meteor, through resisting atmosphere. 1929 Sept. 11. ^{1 page}
- ~~2 pages computation~~
- Vel. sound and Motion of a Meteorite 1930 March 18. 4 pages
- Meteor, p, p, T, hydrodynamic computing 1 page
- The motion of a meteor in its luminous path, from initial fusion to final freezing of the crust. 7 pages 1929
- Schiaparelli, Newton, Didion, Robert mentioned
- Notes on P. S. Epstein; Proc. N. A. S., 17, p. 532 - on the air resistance of projectiles. 1931 1 page
- On the terminal spindle of a meteor trail. 1931 Dec. 13 1 page
- Problem of Orientation of a meteor. Aug 16 1931 1 page
- Elementary treatment of the minimum speed with which a meteor can strike the earth. Oct. 25 1933 2 pages
- Bond Club - Nov. 21 The Paths of Meteors 1927 4 pages
- The Paths of 2 Meteors, Colloquium 1927 May 19 18 pages
- Motion of a Meteor in the Atmosphere 13 pages
- Motion of a Meteor - computation, problems etc. 11 pages
1927 1929

k G
11366
1069

Meteor Mohon con't.

Mohon vertically downward after freezing. Meteor Path 1 page
Resistance prop. to square of velocity. 5 pages

k G
11366
1069

Meteor Trails - Geometrical

H M Phot Hts Lgths 1 2 pages

H Met Phot Hts Lgths 2 1 page

H Met Photo Hts Lgths 3 1 page

H M Phot Hts Lgths 4 1 page

H M Phot Hts Lgths 5 1 page

Curv. Errors 1 1 page

Curv. Errors 2 1 page

Area of a spherical small circle 3 odd pages

Lengths, Heights, and Radiants 5 pages 1925, 1926

Approximation Formulas, Computations 6 pages Oct. 27, 1925

Memo on plate measurement 1924 XII 2X.

~~The question of securing such accuracy (measurement of meteor trails)~~ Deals with the problem of accurate measurement of meteor trails without spending too much time. Author of records influenced by Prof. Schlesinger. 4 pages

Diurnal observation 1928 March 6 2 pages

Observing and Reporting Lunar Eclipses

written material 4 pages crossed out

charts, computation, problems 8 pages

Elkin (Olivier) Figure, Notation, etc. 2 pages

scale factor, Elkin 1 page

Notes on Olivier's paper, etc. 1 page

chart 1 page

Computation 3 pages

Reduction of meteor trails Oct. 15, 1925 7 pages

Spherical Trigonometry with a slide rule - William J. Fisher

Proposed, to graduate on the trigonometre July 8, 1925 2 pages

side of a slide rule SLIDE an additional scale, for the solution of spherical triangles.

Three-place Computation of Zenith Distances - William J. Fisher
4 pages

What can be done — page 2 of discussion on meteor trails.

Pages 1 and 3 apparently missing. Page 2 is crossed out and has computation on the back of it on finding the scale of a stellar photograph. 1 page.

k G

11366

1069

Lunar Eclipses Reports 1927, June 15.

Letter to Dr. Fisher from Prof. W. H. Hoffmann M. D. in Habana, Cuba, 18 July. 25 in which he says he is glad that his observations were useful to Dr. Fisher and requests an explanation of the phenomenon by reflection from the surface of the earth.

Letter to Dr. Fisher from Prof. Hoffman in Habana, Cuba, 17 June 17 in which he briefly describes the lunar eclipse of June 15 in the tropics.

Letter to Dr. Willard J. Fisher from J. T. Watts concerning unusual dark shadows which crossed the moon from East to West. Shadows were perpendicular bands and ^{width was} $\frac{1}{5}$ that of the moon. 8/3/27

Letter to Dr. Fisher from Dr. Stephen Richarz, Professor of Geology, Techny, Illinois. He observed and reported that moon was at no time totally eclipsed. Unusual brightness appeared. June 21, 1927

Letter to Dr. Fisher from James Stokley of Science Service, Inc. June 17, 1927. Stokley observed that "the part of moon nearest the edge of the Umbra appeared very much brighter than the rest of the moon, even at mid totality."

Lunar Eclipses Reports 1927, June 15 con't

- 2 pages letter to Harvard Observatory from E.V. Johnson, Union, Washington June 15, 1927
Observations of eclipse on the 14th Pacific Standard Time.
- Letter to Dr. Fisher from Mrs. Henry Wright, Plymouth, Michigan, June 17, 1927. Observed shadow moving back and forth on moon.
- Letter to Dr. Fisher from R.A. Waldron, Prof. Science at Sluperry Rock State Normal School, June 18, 1927 2 pages ^{inquires about Pons-Winnecke comet.}
- Carbon copy of letter to R.A. Waldron from W.H. Fisher, June 22, 1927.
Reports on Pons-Winnecke Comet.
- Note for Dr. Stapley from William J. Fisher June 20, 1927.
- Observations of Lunar Eclipse 1927 June 15 at Harvard Observatory,
- Letter to Mr. Fisher from A.O. Kuschner, Director, Student's Observatory at University of California, Berkeley Astronomical Dept., June 30, 1927
- Report of June 15 lunar eclipse as observed by Mr. A.E. J. Sneed, 2nd Officer of the U.S. Walton Hall. Forwarded by F.H. Roberts, Commander, U.S. Navy, Acting Hydrographer. Sept. 16, 1927. ^{3 pages}
- Letter to Fisher from Edwin T. Pollock, Capt. U.S. Navy in which he says he is forwarding report of the lunar eclipse and 2 drawings as observed by Miss Margaret Steteville, Phoenix, Arizona. July 1, 1927
- Postcard to Harvard Observatory from Dr. P.A. Young in Bozeman, Montana, June 16, 1927, concerning the lunar eclipse.
- Letter and 2 drawings from Margaret Steteville to U.S. Astronomers, Washington, D.C. 3 pages
- Lunar Eclipse of June 15, 1927, observed at the U.S. Naval Observatory, Washington, D.C., by F.B. Kell. 3 pages
- Letter to Dr. Fisher from Edwin Pollock. June 17, 1927
- Letter to Prof. Fisher from A.E.O. Munsell, Director of Munsell Research Laboratory, Baltimore, Maryland, Sept. 5, 1928.
- Recent Eclipse of the Moon - by A.E.O. Munsell. 3 pages
- Letter from Munsell to Fisher, June 21, 1927
- Carbon copy of letter to A.E.O. Munsell from Fisher, June 24, 1927
- Letter from Munsell to Fisher, June 27, 1927
- Letter from Munsell to Fisher, August 29, 1927
- Carbon copy of letter from Fisher to Munsell, Aug. 30, 1927

Munsell's Problem - lunar eclipse 1927 June 15. To find the mean illumination of the still illuminated lunar crescent at 3 AM E.S.T. 3 pages.

Munsell's Problem - computing Aug 27-30, 1927 6 pages

Munsell's Problem - Cunningham's suggestion, corrected,

Aug. 27, 1927 1 page

Letter ~~to~~ ^{from} Fisher ~~from~~ ^{to} P.C. Keenan, Tucson, Arizona, July 11, 1927

Thanking Fisher for filter photographs of lunar eclipse June 15.

List of Eclipse Plates - lunar eclipse June 15, 1927

Photographs from Steward Obsy. Tucson

2 pages } T Series - 3 plates
2 inch camera using 8x10 Ilford Panchromatic plates

2 pages } Telescope series - 26 plates
36 in. telescope 3 in plates

1 page } Development of telescope plates

lunar eclipse 1927 June 15 list of filters used

chart - 36 in. telescope 26 plates

Letter to Fisher from Philip C. Keenan, Tucson, Arizona, July 16, 1927 concerning photographs of lunar eclipse June 15, 1927

KG

11366

1069

Willard J. Fisher: Manuscripts, Notes and correspondence on Meteors (Much of it material for the monograph he was preparing to write at the time of his death - 1934)

Letter to Fisher from W.S. Crosley, Capt. U.S. Navy, Hydrographer, concerning lunar eclipse of August 14, 1924. (letter - May 11, 1926)

Letter from Fisher to Hydrographic Office, U.S. Navy, in which Fisher thanks them for information on eclipse. (letter - Dec. 22, 1924)

Proposed mailing list for lunar eclipse map, Feb. 8-9, 1925.

Letter to Fisher from F.B. Basset, Cptn. U.S. Navy, Hydrographer

Letter to Hydrographic Office, Washington D.C. from Fisher on subject of lunar eclipse 1925 Feb. 8-9. (letter - Nov. 21, 1924) 3 pages

Statement of information available Nov. 21, 1924 on the Lunar Eclipse 1924 Aug. 14. 3 pages

Letter from Fisher to Hydrographic Office, Navy Dept., Washington, D.C., concerning lunar eclipse 1924 Feb 8-9. (letter - Dec 11, 1924)

Letter from F. B. Basset, Capt. U.S. Navy to Fisher, Dec. 10, 1924

Letter from F. B. Basset, Capt. U.S. Navy to Fisher concerning lunar eclipse of Feb. 8-9, 1925 (letter - Nov. 19, 1924)

Suggested observations of the partial lunar eclipse of Feb. 8-9, to be made by such of the personnel of the U.S. Navy as may be favorably located. 2 pages

Letter from Fisher to Hydrographic Office, Navy Dept. concerning observation of lunar eclipse, 1925 Feb. 8-9. (letter - Oct. 7, 1924)

Lunar Eclipse 1925 Feb. 8-9: Notes on Map of Eclipse 2 pages

Lunar Eclipse 1925 Feb. 8-9: Observations of Weather and Sky, near Woo Chow and in the North Atlantic. 1 page

Letter from Basset, Capt. U.S. Navy to Mr. A. McArdie, Blue Hill Observatory, Harvard University concerning the forwarding of a number of reports on the lunar eclipse. (letter Sept. 25, '24)

Letter to Fisher from Curtis Dev, Sec. of Navy, in which he informs Fisher that instructions have been given to all naval vessels in European and Asiatic waters to take certain observations during August 14th and to report the results to the Hydrographic Office. (letter 28 July 1924)

Letter from Fisher to Sec. of Navy (July 17, 1924) concerning lunar eclipse of Aug. 14, 1924, in which he reiterates a request from Prof. Alexander McArdie to reach ships on the China Station and inform them of the coming eclipse.

Letter from Curtis D. Wilbur^{U.S. Navy Dept} (July 29, 1924) to Alexander McArdie confirming that observations will be made and reported to Hydrographic Office concerning Aug. 14 eclipse lunar eclipse 1924 Aug 14, Weather Reports from Naval Vessels, Aug. 13-14, 1924. Hourly observations before, during, and after lunar eclipse, 14 Aug. 1924. 2 pages

U.S. Asiatic Fleet, Naval Despatch. "1311 Huron will make observations and compute data required by Asiatic Fleet. For 4 hours on August 14th period no other vessels then present at Chefoo need make the observations 1536"

Letter from Miss Anne S. Young, Winona Lake, Indiana, Aug 16, 1922, concerning sun spots maximum.

Letter from Fisher to Mrs. A. S. D. Maunder, Editor, Journal of the British Astronomical Assn, Blenheim, Main Rd, Sidcup, Kent, England, Sept. 4, 1925 concerning block for observation in a former note on reporting lunar eclipses.

Letter to Fisher from A. S. D. Maunder concerning the block, Aug. 22, 1925.

Letter from Fisher to Mrs. Walter Maunder, Aug. 13, 1924, in which he inquires about an ^{original} plate of a lunar eclipse, and if so at what price is it attainable at and if prints can be made from it.

From The History and Survey of the Churches of London and Westminster, the Borough of Southwark, and the Parts adjacent; from the earliest accounts, to the beginning of the year 1770. By a Society of Gentlemen; Revised, corrected, and improved, by Henry Chamberlain of Hatton-Garden, Esq. (Copied by Fisher, Jan. 10, 1934)

KG 11366 1069

Cone Observations 4/12-13/34

M. Shapley, Hoffleit, Johnson, Leary, Watson

- Circumpolar Map for Meteor Observations 12 pages

Hoffleit, ³Leary, ³Cook, ²Watson, ³Johnson, ²Watson, ³Cook, ²Hoffleit, ³Leary, ²Shapley, 14 pages

- 2 charts of all men's (above) observations.

KG

11366

1069 Meteor Glossary

Meteor Glossary of terms as used in the Monograph. 3 pages

Nomenclature 2 pages

Meteor Glossary 2 pages

KG 11366 1069

Harvard Meteorological Monograph

- Computation of the Pole of a Great circle through 2 given points, S_1, S_2 . Oct. 15, 1925. 2 pages
- Computation of the Pole of a Great circle from 2 points. Theory
- Bull's Special Astronomy, computation, May 1, 1926 from G. H. Carrier. 3 pages
- Meteor trails. Conclusion that 3 great circles intersect in a common point. 3 pages
- Solution of Near Isosceles Triangles. 1925 Oct. 11.
- Gravitational Bending of Meteor Trails Sept. 14, 1925
- Position angle of Normal to Trail from Mid-plate.
- The use of the mid plate for the pole of the plate. Dec. 18, 1925.
- Deformation of an angle in central Projection Dec. 20, 1925
- Differential correction for Pole. 1927 Feb. 5
- Doubly photographed Meteors 7 pages
- Lengths of Meteor trails 4 pages
- Calculations and computations on meteor trails 2 pages Oct. 18, 1925
- Computations of meteor trails 4 pages Oct. 1, 1926
- Computations of meteor trails 3 pages Oct. 16, 1926
- Catalogue - individual trails are grouped by series; each series of plates having been taken in general by one lens, this is a grouping in most respects by lenses. 2 pages
- Condition for detonation of a meteor 2 pages
- Audibility of meteors Mar. 18, 1927
- A Mboyo, Miss Desmond. problem on meteor trail.
- Meteor classifications 4 pages
- Outline - Harvard Meteor Photographs
- Harvard Meteor Photographs - Historical Introduction 4 pages
photography proposed by Hais in 1851
W. Zenker, Wolf, Elken, Eaton, Sykora, Blajko, Miss Ames, Miss Howarth,
Collinson, Karmen, Winters

- Bibliography 3 pages
- Meteor lenses 3 pages
- Meteor Cameras 2 pages
- Monograph on Harvard College Observatory Meteor Trails
Photo Reduction - "The measurement and reduction of photo-graphed meteor trails have been discussed only by H. H. Turner, H. A. Newton, and W. L. Elkin." 13 pages
- Meteor Trails on star Trail plates 5 pages
- Harvard Photo Reduction cont'd. 9 pages
- Plate Measurement and Reduction 4 pages
- Figure for tetrahedron method 2 pages
- Point located by triangle of stars. Error of closure in graphical method. 3 pages (crossed out)
- Memo for Dr. Stapley - A revision of report for meteor Comm.
- Spherical triangle problems 3 pages
- Chauvenet p. 39 Eq (174) computation 3 pages
- Meteor Trails photogr. measmt. H. H. Turner. On the measurement of a meteor trail on a photographic plate.
- H. M. Wilson, Topographic surveying... N.Y., Wiley, 1900. Chapter 37 photographic longitudes.
- Photographed Meteor trails - Turner's Method 1929 Oct. 9
- Dyson's (Trépied's) equations 2 pages
- Network Method 5 pages
- Reduction 4 pages
- Harvard Photo. Reduction 7 pages
- Meteor Trails Computing - 2 stars, 2 points on trail solve 2 spherical Δ 's for X, Y, X_2, Y_2 .
- Practice computing Improved approx., 1928 June 19.
Plate E 46564, 1898 Nov. 14.
- Logarithmic Method 3 pages
- Improved approximate solution for p_1, p_2, p_3 June 13, 1928
- Method for mean p . Plate E 46564, 1898 Nov. 14 1928 Sept. 4
4 pages
- Plane approximations for pole, plate center 25 pages
- Finding plate pole from star measurements 5 pages

Harvard Meteorological Monograph cont'd.

- Plate center - approximations, practice computing, 28 pages
- Cunningham's Algebra, checking 1928 June 11 3 pages

KG

11366

1069

Meteor Photography at Ladd Obsy. and elsewhere

- Perseid Campaign, 1932, Exposures, Record watch comparison on this sheet. Camera at Oak Ridge, Harvard, Mass. Aug 11-12, 1932. 3 pages
- Perseid Campaign, 1931, Exposures, Record watch comparison on this sheet, camera at Cambridge, H. C. O. Aug 1931. 3 page
- Perseid Campaign, 1931, shutter camera, Aug. 1931. Point on delta Cassiopeiae, and let the stars drift across the field. 3 pages
- Leonid Campaign, 1931; Out-station. Nov. 14-15, 15-16, 16-17. At 12 PM, point on Pollox; after 7 AM, point on λ Cancer. 9 pages
- Visual observations on Leonids simultaneous with exposure 11 copies.
- Leonid Campaign, 1931. Cambridge station 3 pages
- Leonid Campaign, 1930 Winchester camera Nov. 13-14, 14-15, 15-16, 16-17 At 12, point on η Ursae Majoris. At 1, 2, 3, 4, (and possibly at 5) point on theta Ursae Majoris.
- Orionid Campaign, 1931, Exposures, Record watch comparisons on this sheet. October 19-20, 1931 2 pages
- Quadrantids Campaign, 1931, Exposures, Jan 2-3 at Cambridge. Shutter cameras.
- Perseid Campaign 1931, Nov. 13-14, 14-15, 15-16, 16-17. At 12, point on δ Cass. At 1, 2, 3, 4 (and possibly at 5) point at theta Ursae Majoris. Shutter camera
- Note for Mr. Bowles and Mr. Sawyer, June 23, 1927 on observing instructions.
- Meteor Radiants, Providence, Rhode Is. Data & charts 3 pages
- Meteor Photography: Gemunids, Dec. 10-13.
- Mailing lists for Meteor Photography: Gemunids, Dec. 10-13, 1926
- Equipment to be sent to Ladd Observatory 4 pages
- 2 memos for Dr. Shapley from Fisher, Dec. 3, Dec 10, 1925 concerning Wulward lens.
- Equipment to go to Ladd Obsy. list written by Fisher himself
- Specifications for cleaning and repairs of 2 lenses: both property of the Am. Assn. of Variable Star Observers. Oct. 24, 1926
- Sparse notes on Gemunids Dec. 12-13, 1925
- Radiants & showers in Denning's Catalogue.

- Memo for Dr. Shapley, Oct. 20, 1925 on lenses 2 pages

Notes

Request for Meteor Photography by Fishers Orionids,

nights of Oct. 18-19, 19-20, 20-21 scratchy notes 8 pages

Request for Meteor Photography Leonids Nov. 19, 1931

" " " " " " " " Nov. 13, 1929

" " " " " " " " Nov. 10, 1927

- Andromedes Nov. 13, 1926

Note for Prof. King from Fisher - Leonids Nov. 12, 1927

Request for Meteor photography - Lynxids Apr. 19, 1932

- Gemunids Dec. 10, 1930

" " " " " " " " " " "

Dec. 9, 1929

Dec. 4, 1928

Dec. 11, 1926

Dec. 10, 1927

Meteor work nights of Dec. 10-11 to 12-13, 1925

Request for meteor photography Quadrantids Dec. 29, 1930

Dec. 31, 1929

Jan. 2, 1929

Dec. 30, 1926

Aug. 10, 1931

Aug. 9, 1930

Perseids

Aug. 8, 1929

Aug. 5, 1929

Aug. 8, 1928

~~Perseids~~

Aug. 9, 1926

all meteor exposures Dec. 10, 1929

re announcement card 127 May 22, 3

Quadrantid Meteors notes

3 Aquarids notes 1926 July 28 2 pages

Perseid radiants, Providence, Obsy. notes

Request for Meteor Photography June 2, 1930 for nights June 7-8, 8-9, 9-10, for predicted comet and shower.

2 Harvard Obsy. Announcement cards.

#127 - Schwassmann - Wachmann Comet May 19, 1930

#128 - Meteoric Shower. May 22, 1930

- Comet d. 1930 scratchy notes

KG 11366 1069 Miscellaneous

- J. F. Boyenberq, Die Sternschnupper, 1839. shooting stars 8 pages
- Metcalf's Research 1927 Oct 15 F9474 on E9323 plates
- Harvard Meteor Photographs, Historical Introduction 7 pages
- Harvard Meteor Photographs, lenses 3 pages
- Harvard Meteor Photographs, Cameras 2 pages
- " " " , Bibliography 3 pages
- " " " , Reduction 17 pages
- " " " , Heights, lengths 3 pages
- lens notes, approximations, small chart 1/2 2 pages
- A. F. Lewin Observatory, 45, p. 102-103, 1922, the use of the slide rule as an auxiliary to the solution of Kepler's equation
- Graphical searching for Periods in Irregular Data 1930 June 14
- Meteor ~~obs~~ observation charts 2 pages
- Queries on Kundemann and Dobson, Meteors 3 pages
- Computation of Vaporization rate 4 pages
- Hoffmeister, Die Himmelswelt, 34. p. 143-148, 1924 2 pages
- Neue Beiträge zur Theorie der Sternschnuppen
- Theory of Meteors, Energy transformation schedule for all meteors. 1924 XII 11.
- Meteor Theory, Any physical theory of meteors must start from the following energy relation: ... 3 pages
- ^{mann} Kundemann and Dobson Revision 7 pages
- Field Areas of cameras 1927 July 29
- Publication of Meteor observations 1926 Nov 2 3 pages
- Meteor Problems 1926 Nov 12 Band club 2 pages
- Astr. colloquium, 1926 Oct 13, The audibility of sounds, the composition of the atmosphere, & meteors 3 pages
- Note for Dr. Shapley from Fisher concerning bibliography of meteors, 1930 (note - 1931 Nov 21)

271	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
272	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
273	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
274	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
275	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
276	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
277	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
278	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
279	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
280	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
281	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
282	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
283	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
284	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
285	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
286	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
287	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
288	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
289	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
290	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
291	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
292	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
293	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
294	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
295	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
296	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
297	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
298	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
299	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2
300	Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society	1931	2

- Note for Fisher from Shapley, June 1, 1931, concerning bibliography of papers on meteors & related topics published under 1930.
- A partial bibliography of papers on meteors and related topics, published under date 1930. 6 pages

KG 11366. 1070
 W. J. Fischer
 Correspondence
 1927 JUNE 15
 - (LUNAR ECLIPSE)

SUNRISE - SUNSET line across NORTH AMERICA at MID - eclipse 3 pages
 Note for Dr. Shapley Feb. '27

Points on SUNRISE - SUNSET LINE - Alaska

Letter to US. Weather Bureau, Seattle, Washington - Observations relating
 to LUNAR ECLIPSE 2 pages April 5

Observations desired at mid - eclipse June

Letter to US Weather Bureau, Seattle - follow-up to April 5 letter April 8

Response from Seattle's US Weather Bureau giving means of getting in
 touch with Alaskan points along sunrise - sunset line

Letter to Ralph C. Mize, Meteorologist, US Weather Bureau at Juneau
 requesting assistance - Fisher needs observers stationed within a
 hundred miles of sunrise - sunset line 2 pages Apr. 12

Response from RC Mize - Weather Bureau observers were contacted and
 informed - lists observation points Apr. 27

Thank - you note to Mize May 7

Note from Edward C. Phillips of Georgetown University Aug. 30

" " James Stokley of Science Service, Inc., Washington, D.C.

" to Science Service

Cablegram from Stokley

Letter to Stokley

Letter to Fisher

Note for Dr. Shapley

Letter to Stokley

" " Fisher

" " Stokley

all above correspondence of April - June regarding arrangements
 for observation in southwestern states]

(2)

- Note for Dr. Shapley concerning methods of plotting and computing eclipse Jan.
- mailing list for appeals for observations
- The LUNAR ECLIPSES of 1927 3 pages draft
also 2 page handwritten copy
- Correspondence between Fishw and JE Hemphill, Chief Signal Officer, War Dept., Washington, D.C., concerning setting up of observation stations - info. regarding observation points in Alaska
- Observations at Mid-Eclipse June 14
- Letter to Hemphill regarding methods of observation
My response from Hemphill
- Weather observations at Mid-Eclipse (June 14) accompanied by note from Fishw explaining them
- The LUNAR ECLIPSES of 1927 - 3 pages - info. regarding eclipse and request for observations
- Letter to Macmillan and Co. in London regarding publication of above, stressing need for wide publicity March
above will be published in Popular Astronomy - letter from CH Gingrich, Editor
- request for observations to Fairbanks Daily News-Miner April
- letters to Mr. Lawrence Richardson ~~and~~ evidently closely related with the JOURNAL(?) in England) and Editor of Gazette Astronomique requesting publication of Proposed Observations Relating to the LUNAR ECLIPSE

The following correspondence of March, 1927

- ┌ - letter to ~~main~~ radio station KDKA, West Pittsburgh, Pa. asking for report on observations in Baker Lake region through the radio station

Canada

- letter from Canadian Westinghouse Company, Ltd. in Montreal, Quebec concerning radio messages from Baker Lake region 2 pages
- letter from director of IC Obsy. C(?) ~~main~~ acknowledging receipt of Canadian Westinghouse letter 1 page
- letter to GA Wendt at Canadian Westinghouse - info. concerning eclipse 1 page
- letter from C. Westinghouse to R. Meldrum Stewart, Director of the Dominion Obsy. in Ottawa, Ont. - brief history of Canadian Westinghouse recommendation of KDKA for transmitting observations 2 pp. (copy of original)

(3)

- 1 page letter to GA Wendt of Can. West. - Fisher plans to carry out the project on a larger scale
- 1 page to KDKA - their services are not needed at the present; will be notified if there is something for them to do
- 1 page from KDKA - awaiting instructions from Wendt
- 1 page from Can. West. about transfer of technical info. and observers
- 1 page to Wendt of Can. West. - location of receiving sets]

April '27
Correspondence

- 4 letters (4 pp.) from Hudson's Bay to Can. West. - all applaud the fine reception of KDKA radio programs (sent in Jan; received in March)
- 1 page from Can. West. listing good receiving points and advising that Fisher contact Mounted Police, Hudson's Bay Co., Rev. Bishop A. Turquetil of Montreal, Revillon Frères Trading Co. (copies)
- 1 page to Wendt - Fisher took his advice
- 1 page from Wendt acknowledging reliability of KDKA; location of observers
- 1 page from Can. West. to Revillon Frères Trading Co. - broadcasts concerning eclipse will go out to Baker Lake (copy)
- 1 page from Can. West. to Dominion Obsy. - as soon as authorization is secured, broadcasting will begin] → (copy)
- Feb. 1928 - letter from Can. West. - inquiring whether or not anything came of the broadcasts 1 page
- to Can. West. - the project was a success: observations received 1 page
- 3 page draft of The Lunar Eclipses of 1927
- 1 page galley proof of above article
- 1 page from Meteorological Office of the Air Ministry in London - notice is too short to reach commanders of ships with requests for observations
- postcard from Lewis J. Boss of Seagrave Obsy. in R.I. asking if he could be of assistance June 7, '27
- reply to Boss - The conditions are not favorable for extensive observa-

tion in Northeastern US - rather than waste plates and ~~prepare~~ photoelectric cells, just enjoy spectacle 1 page JUNE, '27

May correspondence

1 page from Edwin Carpenter of University of Arizona - observations will be made by students

letter (1 p.) to Carpenter - thank-you for co-operation; all work is experimental

2 letters (2 pages) to Steward Obsy. at University of Arizona and Joaquin Gallo of National Obsy. at Tacubaya, Mexico requesting that observations of the eclipse be made (a form letter)

1 page from Gallo in Mexico - he will observe (addressed to Shapley - direct of the obsy.)

1 page from Gallo to Fisher - conditions may not be favorable for observation, but he will make an attempt (humorous English)

1 page to Gallo requesting the negatives rather than copies

1 page handwritten from Earle Linsley of Chabot Obsy. in Oakland, Cal.

The night may be foggy, but he will try to make observations June 1

3 form letters to Chabot Obsy.; Prof. A.O. Leuschner, Director Students' Obsy. at Berkeley; Dr. V.M. Slipher, Director of the Lowell Obsy. at Flagstaff, Arizona - requesting that they observe the eclipse (May)

1 page to Imperial Marine Obsy. in Kobe, Japan - request for observation
Mar. 20

1 p. from R. Meldrum ^{Stewart} ~~Stewart~~ of Dominion Obsy. - how to get in touch with Baker Lake (March, '27)

1 p. to Stewart - Fisher getting in touch w/ KDKA

1 p. from Stewart - more possibilities for communicating w/ Baker Lake

copies of 2 letters: GA Wendt of Canadian Westinghouse to Hoyes Lloyd, Sec. Canadian National Parks, Ottawa, Ont.

Hoyes Lloyd to Stewart

both letters concerned with communication w/ Baker Lake (3 pages)

2 p. letter to Stewart from Fisher - plans to expand project due to so many offers of help

1 p. from Stewart - arrangements for communication and observation

1 p. to Stewart from Fisher - has sent requests for observations to Hudson's Bay Co, Revillon Freres Trading Co., Rev. Turquetil (Bishop of Hudson Bay)

5

- 1 p. from Stewart - concerned with arrangements
- 1 p. " " to Hudson's Bay Co. in Montreal - the Company has offered to help with the project
- enclosed copy of Proposed Broadcast
- 1 page. to Stewart from Fisher - further arrangements
- handwritten note from Shapley - wants broadcast posted on bulletin board
- Stewart 1 p. letter - sending copy of final broadcast
- Eclipse Broadcast - 2 pages
- 1 p. thanks to Stewart - broadcast satisfactory

May correspondence

- 1 page Fisher to Stewart - plans to have appeal for observations published in Canada
- 1 page from Stewart - meteorological stations would be more help
- message for Mounted Police and Hudson's Bay Co. at Fort Good Hope
- 1 p. from Fisher to Stewart - arrangements for observations in Canada and Southwest
- 1 p. (copy) from F. Stupart, Director Meteorological Service, to Stewart - sending list of Meteorological Stations
- list of Stations (copy)
- form letter "LUNAR Eclipse of June 15, 1927" - appeal for observations
- 1 p. from Stewart to Fisher - has checked out Stupart's list of stations and found them to be satisfactory
- 1 p. from Stewart to Stupart (copy) - sending copies of a note to be distributed to stations
- 1 p. from Fisher to Stewart - arrangements in Canada complete
- 1 p. Stewart to Fisher - sending reports of Canadian observations 7/26/27
- 1 p. to Stewart - Weather Service to fill in gaps; little response from southwest
- 1 p. from Stewart - more reports Sept. 8
- handwritten note for Dr. Shapley from Fisher - wants him to read Canadian reports Sept.
- 2 pp. to Stewart - thank-you for co-operation; also about Aug 10 in five days

- 1 p. from Stewart - sending another report Sept.
- 1 p. to Stewart - Thanks for report - useful
- 1 p. from Stewart - sending prints of photographs of eclipse from northern observer Oct. '27
- Handwritten note from Fisher to Stewart - report from Chesterfield Inlet not too late
- 1 p. from Stewart - sending above report May, '28
- "Instrumental Observations Relating to the Total Lunar Eclipse, 1927 June 15" 2 pages
- handwritten draft of above 2 pages
- April correspondence - 1 p. from Rev. A. Turgetil of Chesterfield Inlet - glad to help with observations
- 2 p. from Fisher to Turgetil asking for his co-operation
- 1 p. from Cortlandt Starnes, Commissioner of Mounted Police - will make arrangements w/ Stewart for directions to northern detachments of police
- 1 p. Fisher to Starnes - wants weather, cloud, and sky info. from certain observation points
- "Total Lunar Eclipse of 1927 June 15" 2 pp.
- 1 p. from Hudson's Bay Co. - will work on plans with Stewart
- 2 pp. from Fisher to Hudson's Bay Co. - appeal for observations
- 1 p. from Revillon Frères Trading Co. - probably will not be able to contact Baker Lake
- 2 pp. from Fisher to Revillon Frères - appeal for observations
- 1 p. from CA Chant of U. of Toronto - plans for publicizing the eclipse work
- 1 p. from Alexander McArdie of Harvard U. Bwe Hill Obsy. - advises Fisher to contact Chant of U. of Toronto for he will get many observers for him
- 1 p. from Hydrographic Office in Washington, DC from WS Crosley, Captain, US Navy - will publish eclipse article in Hydrographic Bulletin
- 1 p. Fisher to Hydrographic Office - thank you

WJ Fisher LUNAR Eclpse - Literature

Solar Spectrum - Telluric lines, outside A, B, a 2 pages

MOON'S rotation, taken from RS Ball, Spherical Astronomy, Cambridge, 1908

" 2 pages of notes

LOW SUN and eclipse illustrations "

A. Berget, Le Ciel 3 pages

LUNAR Eclpse directions

J. Gwyn Elger, JBAA, 5, p. 249, 1895.

Total Eclipse of the MOON, 1895, March 10. 2 pages

LUNAR Eclipses

Sir JFW Herschel, Outlines of Astronomy, 1872, 10th ed. 6 pages

LUNAR Eclpse 1844 2 pages (source - F. de Vico) Italian

LUNAR Eclpse 1870 VII 12 2 sources 3 pages (Buffham, Johnson)

" " 1877 2 sources 4 pages (Todd, Sternbeck)

" " 1877 (Capron) 4 pp.

" " 1877 (Observatory) 4 pp.

" " 1880 (Russell, Observatory) 2 pp.

1884 x 4 Flammarion 4 pp.

" " (L'ASTRONOMIE) 2 pp.

" " (Johnson) "

" " (Lowe, Nature) "

LUNAR Eclpse 1887 Lescaubault 2 pp. French

chart - 1888 Contacts, reduced to grit (?)

LUNAR Eclpse 1888 L'ASTRONOMIE 1 page

" " " " La Nature 2 pp.

" " " " Perry 3 pp.

" " " " Pickering, ANN. HC OBS 2 pp.

" " " " L'ASTRONOMIE, Trambloy 4 pp.

" " 1889 A. Riccio and A. Mascori 4 pp. Italian

" " 1892 M. Wolf 2 pp. German

" " 1892 W. Doderck " "

" " " HC Russell "

" " 1895 T. Gwyn Elger, MEMOIRS BAA 4 pp.

1895 JHR Salmon, MEMOIRS BAA 2 pp.

everything below is handwritten (the majority) notes from periodicals and books - all info. concerns observations on eclipses of the moon in years cited

list of cities and observation times (chart) of 1884 eclipse

~~XX~~
~~XX~~

LUNAR Eclipse 1898 GA., Bulletin Soc. Astronomique Fr. 6 pp. eclipse of Jan. 7

LUNAR Eclipse 1898 - July 5th GA., Bull. Soc. Astr. Fr. 8 pp.

" " " " "GA." " 3rd " " 1 pp.

" " " " " E. Stuyvaert, ANN. de l'Obs. roy. de Belgique 2 pp.

L.E. 1898 Bull. Soc. Astr. Fr. 1 page eclipse of Dec. 27

" " W. Goodacre, JBA A 3 pp. " " "

" " Th. ~~Moreux~~ Moreux, Bull. Soc. Astr. Fr. 1 page Dec. 27th

" " W. Sidgreaves Dec. 27 eclipse 2 pp. eclipse

" " - Dec. 27 A. Straus, M. Mandler 2 pp.

" X " - " " " E. Stuyvaert 2 pp.

" " " " " M. Wolf, Astr. Nachr. 2 pp.

graph of M. Wolf - evidently showing position of MOON at various times -
" indicates brightest and reddest spots

LUNAR Eclipse 1899 EM. T., Bull. Soc. Astr. Fr. 4 pp.

1902 HA Howe, Popular Astronomy - observ. of students of
University of Denver of eclipse of Oct 16, 1902 1 page

LE 1902 EE Barnard, Astr. Nachr. 3 pp.

LE 1903 A Miller, Astr. Nachr. 2 pp.

LE 1903 - April Quénisset, Bull. Soc. Belge d'Astr. 2 pp.

LE 1906 GF., Bull. Soc. Astr. Fr. 4 pp.

LE 1903 SA Saunders, JBAA 3 pp.

LE 1909 Bull. Soc. Astr. Fr. 3 pp.

" " N V Givori, Rivista di Astronomia 6 pp.

" 1910 P. Chopardet and Goudey, Bull. Soc. Astr. Fr. 2 pp.

" " AA Nijland, J. van der Bilt, Astr. Nachr. 2 pp.

" " F. Quénisset, F. Baldet, Bull. Soc. Astr. Fr. 2 pp.

" " M. Wolf, Astr. Nachr. 2 pp.

" 1917 Bull. Soc. Astr. Fr. 7 pp.

" 1920 L'Abbe Moreux, Revue du Ciel 2 pp.

" " ET, Bull. Soc. Astr. de Fr. 6 pp.

" " Copy of Record in The Observatory Journal

" " Edward H. Collinson, extracts from private letter to

(3)

Mr. Lawrence Richardson 1 page

flip side - F. QUÉNISSET, Bull. Soc. Astr. Fr. 1 page May 3, 1920
eclips

- Total LUNAR Eclipse -

- October 26th - 27th, 1920 -

observed at GOULBURN, New South Wales

" by MIRIAM S. CHISHOLM

4 sheets of charts, drawings, and handwritten notes

also included: note explaining this report to LE RICHARDSON, member of
British Astronomical Assn.

LUNAR Eclipse 1921 Bull. Soc. Astr. Fr. 4 pp.

" " " 4 pp. (another report)

" " J. HOPMANN, Astr. Nachr 4 pp.

also: 2 graphs of umbra

LUNAR Eclipse 1921 L'Abbé TH. MOREUX, Revue du ciel 1 page

" " 1924 M. HAUPTMANN, Ciel et Terre 4 pp.

" " " Bevioty (typed) 2 pp.

" " " L. CAP., Gazette Astronomique 2 pp.

" " " AM. DERMUL, Gazette Astronomique "

" " " M. HAUPTMANN + I. PANIS, Ciel et Terre 2 pp.

" " " F. de ROY, Gazette Astronomique 2 pp.

LUNAR Eclipse Feb. 8th, 1925 Copy of Record in the Obsy. Journal
2 pp.

①

Folder: Geocentric Paths

2 pages concerning measuring engines and reseaux evidently used in making photographic plates of stars

the first page is missing

2 pages of algebra related to tetrahedrons - these pages, I believe, have something to do with the above

Reduction of Meteor Trails on Star-trail plates July 16, 1927 3pp.

Photographed Meteor Trails - measurement 2 pages

Reduction of Meteor Trails on Star-trail Plates

(it seems that pages are lost for the last sentence is cut off)

7 pages of trigonometry - handwritten

2 small pages of trigonometry

11 pages of drafts of an article on the identifiable peculiarities of meteors photographed at two stations

part handwritten, part typed

cross-outs and much rewriting

8 page handwritten draft of article on determination of meteor heights

5 pages of Meteor Heights, Computing Form Sept., 1926

Meteor trail w/ reseau or rectangular measuring machine June 29, 1928

1 page

1 page of geometry on poles of trails and poles of plates

Methods for Computing Meteor Heights 1 page

1. Sq. problem. Comstock. solved by determinants 1 page

drawing related to above - stated problem of meteors photographed at two stations

Geocentric Meteor Paths 1 page (corners missing) typed

Parallax Plates 1898 4 pages

1 page trigonometry

(2)

Focal Length of lens - 1 page trigonometry

Computing Form for Poles of Meteor Trails on Star-trail Plates 2 pages

paper (handwritten) on meteor paths - problem stated and solved (find poles of each trail if paths are straight lines and have two photographed trails)

Dec 26, 1930 4 pages

~~another draft of the above problem~~

another draft of the above problem 4 pages (typed)

Meteor Heights - computing form Sept., 1926 2 pages

3 pages regarding the Leonid shower of Nov. 14, 1898; handwritten

(1)

Folder: NO title

(1)

all this should read from bottom up

- MEMO ON references for Dr. Shapley 3 pp.

- 1 page from CG Abbot of Smithsonian - cannot publish paper on Spectrum of the Eclipsed Moon May 6, 1924

- letter to Smithsonian requesting publication of above paper

April, '24

- note from CG Abbot returning on request an original drawing of Fisher's

- request to Smithsonian for return of drawing

- thank-you letter to Smithsonian for copies of Fisher's article on LUNAR Eclipses

Feb., '24

- 1 page from CG Abbot - advance copies of "The Brightness of Lunar Eclipses" to be sent to Fisher

- Fisher wants copies of ms paper

- request to Smithsonian for return of drawing; corrections on proofs of paper

- letter to Abbot - corrections and additions JAN, '24

- Smithsonian sending copies when received from printer; engraving of photograph to accompany paper lost JAN.

- Fisher's request for copies Dec., '23

- 3 copies of what kind of info. is required when observations of meteors are sent to HC Osby

- 1 p. from SR Williams of Am. Asso. for the Advancement of Science - Fisher will not be able to present an abstract of a paper at the Asso. meeting Dec., '23

- entry on Fisher in AMERICAN MEN OF SCIENCE - Fourth Edition 1 p.

- 1 p. to Dr. Burton E. Livingston ^{of Smithsonian} - Fisher wants to enter his paper on The Brightness of Lunar Eclipses in competition for a \$1000 prize Dec., '23

all December, '23 correspondence

- 1 p. from Livingston - he can not submit a summary of his paper - he must read it at a meeting of Am. Asso. for the Advancement of Science too late to submit a paper to be read at Cincinnati meeting

- 1 p. to Prof. Otto Koppius, Secretary of AAAS - Fisher is sending an abstract of his paper for the Cincinnati meeting

- 1 p. to Dr. CF Brooks of Clark University - Fisher needs a member of the Am. Meteorological Society to present his paper in Cincinnati

(2)

- 1 p. - Brooks has placed paper on program of meeting under auspices of Meteorological Society

- 1 p. from Francis D. Munaghan, Sec. of AAAS - Fisher will receive Proceedings volume and Directory

Folder

The Structure of the Earth's Shadow 55' to 57'

- Lunar Eclipses 1860-1922
- Dates and Horizontal Parallaxes 1 p.
- observations on lunar eclipses from 1860-1922 from different observation points 52 pages

Folder

The Structure of the Earth's Shadow 58' to 61'

- Lunar Eclipses 1860-1922
- Dates and Horizontal Parallaxes 1 p.
- observations on lunar eclipses from 1860-1922 from observation points within a different range than the above 83 pages

Folder

Earth's Shadow

Tables and Introduction

- Condition of the shadow in Total Eclipse 3 pp.
- 78 Lunar Eclipses 1860-1922 Arranged in order of Horizontal Parallax 3 pp.
- Condition of the shadow in Total Eclipses 3 pp.
- Dark Spot 1860-1922 1 small page
- "Summaries still to make" 1 small page
- Total Eclipses

(1)

- The Structure of the Earth's Shadow FROM LUNAR Eclipses 1860-1922 8 pp.
- LUNAR Eclipses 1860-1922 2 pp.

Folder :

- Mailing List
- Correspondence on Eclipses
- 1 p. from Frank Sargent - is supplying info. on eclipse of Feb., 1924 Sept., '25 handwritten
- 2 pp. to Mr. RG Chandra of India - Fisher wants info. on eclipse of Feb., '24 (JUNE, '24)
- 3 pp. from Chandra reporting what he had observed
- 1 p. to Dr. Leonardo J. Palice of Cebu, Samar - wants info. on eclipse of 2/24 (JUNE, '24)
- 1 p. from Palice - supplies info. on eclipse March '24

May, '24

- 3 pp. from Miriam Chisholm to Richardson - info. on eclipse of 2/24
- 3 pp. of notes by Chisholm on eclipse
- 1 p. of drawings of eclipse
- 1 p. from Alexander Macfie of Blue Hill Obsy. of Harvard at Readville, Mass. - on article in Meteorological Magazine about 2/24 eclipse; wants Fisher to present work on August eclipse
- 1 p. to Sr. J. Comas-Sola at The Obsy. Fabra, Barcelona, Spain asking for info. on eclipse of Nov. 15, 1891 (Aug., '24)
- handwritten note from Sr. J. Comas-Sola - she could not find the observations she had made
- 1 p. to William Abbot of Societe Astr. de France, Athens, Greece - wants info. on eclipse of 3/3/23 (July, '24)
- W. Abbot 1 p. handwritten letter supplies requested eclipse info.
- copy of report of WS Franks of Brockhurst Obsy., Sussex, Eng. on

(4)

11/16/10 eclipse

- 2 copies (4 pages) of a letter to the Editor of the Honolulu T.H. (?) requesting observations of the approaching eclipse of Aug. 25-26
- 1 p. from Edwin H. Bryan of Bernice Pauahi Bishop Museum of Polynesian Ethnology and Natural History in Honolulu - he submits info on eclipse
- Partial Eclipse of the Moon
August 25-26, 1923
(Copy of notes made by Bryan at U. of Hawaii Obsy.) 4 pp.
- 4 photographs of eclipse
- 1 p. to Editor of Science - Fisher directs attention of AAAS to deficiencies in Am. records of lunar eclipses (July, 1924) wants his list of lunar eclipses published
- response from J. Mark Cattill, Ed. of Science - no room for list
- 1 p. memorandum for Dr. Shapley - Fisher talks of publication of his paper on lunar eclipses (Sept., '24)
- 1 p. from F.K. Richtmyer - he will read Fisher's paper at Circinnati meeting of AAAS (Richtmyer - Dept. of Physics, Cornell U.) Dec., '23
- flip side - thank-you note to Richtmyer
- 1 p. letter from Joel H. Metcalf, Minister First Parish Church, Portland, Me. - concerning apertures (handwritten) (Mar., '24)
- 2 pp. letter from Metcalf about lunar eclipses " (handwritten)
- 2 page letter to Metcalf about photographs of the eclipses
- 1 p. note from Metcalf - about photographs (Nov., '23)
- 2 p. note from Metcalf on photographing the path of the moon (Nov., '23)
- 2 p. letter to Dr. Chr. Jensen, Germany - answer to a question raised by Jensen on Fisher's paper on lunar eclipses (July, '26)
- 1 p. letter from Jensen - in German (July, '26)
- postcard from Prof. Plessmann (?) - in German: about color of moon
- 1 p. from Jensen in German ~~xxxxxxxxxx~~ (June, '26)
- 1 p. to Jensen - Fisher sending copies of 2 of his papers

①

Folder :

Notes on Observing and Reporting LUNAR ECLIPSES

Spectrum of Eclipsed MOON

graph of Solar Spectrum

LUNAR ECLIPSES 1860-1922 - list 2 pages

"Notes on Observing and Reporting LUNAR ECLIPSES" 8 pages

2 copies of above 16 pages

Note from Dr. Shapley commending Fisher for outlining the work for observing + reporting eclipses 4/24

Notes on Observing + Reporting LUNAR ECLIPSES

part typed, part handwritten 8 pages 4/24

"The Spectrum of the Eclipsed MOON" 15 pages (as numbered)

actually 17 pages

LUNAR ECLIPSE PHOTOGRAPHS - SEARCH LIST

2 copies of page 1 (drafts)

2 copies page 8

2 copies page 8a - also footnotes to page 1

Folder :

LUNAR ECLIPSE 1927 JUNE 15

May - June, '27

1 page letter from G. Blum of Societe' Astronomique de France - asks if Fisher observed eclipse of Dec. ~~1926~~ 19, 1926.

1 p. to Blum - Fisher gives all info. he has on above eclipse

1 p. response from Blum - Thank - you

- page from Bulletin of AAAS (?) - The Total LUNAR ECLIPSE of 1927 Dec. 8

- 4 p. letter from RG Chandra in India - observations on eclipse of Dec. 8, '27

- letter from JE Hemphill of Signal Corps in Washington - is sending weather conditions during eclipse of April 17, '27
- Weather Observations at Mid - Eclipse - reports on 11 radio stations in Alaska (4 pages)
- list of cities in Canada
- 2 photographs of sun setting over ocean - Oct 13, '27
- Dr. Stupans
- letter from director of Meteorological Service in Toronto - enclosing note from Dominion Obsy. about June 15 eclipse
- handwritten note from Dominion observer
- 3 page letter from Dominion Experimental Station to Meteorological Service - observations on eclipse
- handwritten note from JC Cassidy, observer at Chatham, NB, Canada - weather report at time of eclipse
- form letter sent out by Rev. J. Ph. L'Atalieu (? or Italian) concerning reporting of observations of eclipse of 6/15/27
- letter from Gull Pulp & Paper Co. in Clarks City, Quebec reporting to Meteorological Service weather conditions during eclipse
- letter to Dominion Obsy. from CB Hines, Supt. of Power Plant of Bathurst Company Limited, reporting observations on eclipse
- 2 p. letter from WA Dinwoode of Richmond Gulf Post of Hudson's Bay Co. to District Manager reporting observations
- 1 p. from L. Ducharme of Roman Catholic Mission at Chesterfield Inter, Canada to Dominion Obsy. reporting eclipse
- 2 pp. from M.A. Joyce of Chesterfield Inter Detachment of Hudson's Bay Police to Commanding Officer in Ottawa reporting observations
- letter from Joyce to Commanding Officer reporting that he had received the radio message regarding eclipse - will undertake observations (May, '27)
- letter from Director of HC Obsy (?) to Col. Cortland Starnes, Commissioner of Police in Ottawa thanking him for Joyce's report (copy)
- letter from Port Harrison reporting on eclipse (copy)
- letter from Baker Lake " " " "

- letter from REVISON FRÉVES Trading Co. - sending above two reports from two posts (sent to Dominion Obsy.)
- telegraph to Dominion Obsy. from HUDSON'S BAY Co. post at Fort Good Hope
- reporting eclipse

- letter from RC Mize, Meteorologist of US Dept. of Ag. in JUNEAU, Alaska - sending reports on eclipses received from observers
 6 reports: Bethel, Circle, Eagle, Fort Yukon, Rampart, Tanana
- letter from RF Stupans, Director Meteor. Serv., Toronto - weather report at points in Canada at time of eclipse (Jan., '28)
- letter from Fisher to Stupans requesting weather conditions 2 pp.

- copy of Gazette Astronomique of May, '27 3 pages
 article on eclipse of June 15
- page from Bulletin of AAAS - "Proposed Observations relating to the LUNAR ECLIPSE, 1927 June 15" by Willard J. Fisher
- news items on eclipse
 Boston Sunday Advertiser 1927 June 5 "Radio to throw new light on Moon's Eclipse"
 Boston Herald June 11, '27 "Boston to see Total Eclipse"
 Boston Advertiser 1927 June 12 "Total Eclipse of Moon comes on Wed."
 The Montreal Daily Star April 30, '27 "Mounted Police and Radio will enable Astronomers to gather data on Eclipse"
 "Where the LUNAR Eclipse can be observed"
 Boston Transcript 1927 June 3 "Shadowing the shadowed Moon"
 " " 1927 June 2 "Total Eclipse of Moon on June 15 is visible here"
 Boston Evening Transcript 6/1/27 "The skies in June"
 Boston Transcript May 21, '27 "Canadian Mounted to help Harvard in Eclipse observation"
 Hydrographic Bulletin (Wash., D.C.) April 6, '27 "The LUNAR Eclipses of 1927"

Boston Transcript 6/15/27 "Harvard Catches Brief Glimpse of Eclipse of Moon"
 Boston Herald 1927 May 1 "Radio Asks Arctic to Watch Eclipse"
 galleyproof of "The Lunar Eclipses of 1927"
 Boston Herald June 16, 1927 "Cloud Banks Obscure Eclipse of Moon"

- letter from Philip S. Fiske of Boston Advertiser - sending copy of article he wrote on talk w/ Fisher (June 9, '27)
- copy of article - 4 pages
- copy of Daily Science News Bulletin of Wash. D.C. - "Canadian Mounted Police to Aid Eclipse Observations" 2 pages
- copy of another article - "Moon Eclipse Offers Chance for Amateurs" 3 pages
- page from Science News - Letter, May, 28, '27 - "Observe Moon Eclipse in Arctic"
- The Lunar Total Eclipse of 1927 June 15" by Willard J. Fisher 19 pages
corrected copy

Folder:

- all loose papers clumped together
- 24 pages of: error analyses ~~notes~~
 approximate and exact trajectories
 perspective curves

(5)

- Curvature of Meteor Path - Mailing list
- 2 photographs July 26, 1930
- "The Curvature of a Meteor Path" by Willard J. Fisher and GZ Dimitroff (6 pages)
- "The Curvature of the Photographed Trail of a Meteor" rough draft (5 pages)

A1 20401 Meteor
GZD July 1930

COMPARISON STAR PAIRS - charts 2 pages
26 pages ON STAR PAIRS - charts, calculations

Folder: Notes and Computing on the Velocity of Light 1917

- 57 pages of computations and notes
- 1 p. letter from Baker Box Co. in Worcester - info. about boxes and a trough on legs

Folder: loose stuff together

- Notebook page from April 22 and 23, 1918
- H.C.O. Meteor Trails Computation (E 4623 - Nov 14, 1898) ^{plate}
pages 17-38, seems that 1-16 are missing

The End

FOLDER: Fireball Report
1925-1932
 typed

Bright Meteors reported to
Harvard College Observatory

1925-1932

by ^{and} William J. Fisher

(body of report)

(letters, etc.)

(73) typed ~~pages~~ pages. Total # pp. in folder: (82) /

paper gives details of all meteors - except in special cases - at least as bright as Sirius or Procyon, which have been reported to Harvard College Observatory from 1925 Nov. 1 to 1932 Dec. 31, provided that the meteor could have been readily observed from the New England region. . . ."

- Writer mentions cooperation of Assoc. Press in sending out brief questionnaires to their subscribers, in order to reach observers. Letters received from observers indexed + abstracted.

- Necessity of reaching public immediately after a fireball apparition; Describes efforts by the writer to reach public in this way through press broadcast, etc.

- Description of standard Questionnaire and of recording of observations.

p. 2 Table of appeals sent out & communications received as a result of press appeals.

p. 9. Table showing "tendency toward accuracy in the apparently vague estimates of moment of apparition"

Catalogue of abstracts of reports received, beginning p. 12.

Resumé of the statistics of this catalogue of bright meteors: Total meteors: 256

Meteors observed at night, after midnight:

W 75°, 34, 13 per cent

(Meteors, Resumé of Statistics in Catalogue of Reports)

Meteors observed in evening at or before 8³⁰ pm: W 75°, 129, 50 percent)

Final altitudes $\geq 30^\circ$, 107 cases, 40 percent; nearly horizontal.

Paths observed, mostly at low altitudes, 34, 13 percent;

Tails reported, 67, 25 %;

Trains reported, 30, 11 %.

Sparks 39, 15 %

Breaking 38, 14 %

p.12 Table of Final quadrants determined.

[Colors] inaccurate list

Meteors seen in daylight, 2; detonating meteors, 2; radiant determined, 4.

p.13 - Begins list of abstracted reports by Observers.

p.73 Last report, date 1932 Dec. 22
8:14 PM, W 75°.

Note (typed) to Dr. Fisher from H.S., dated 2/23/34
"consider poss. of Watson taking following work on bright meteors"

Note (hand wr.) to Dr. Shapley from Dr. Fisher 1933 Sept 11
on value of the report - statistically, little.
Results disappointingly meager, but educational value
as a study in collection of data.

Note^{typed} to Dr. Shapley from C.C. Wylie, Feb. 14, 1934
regarding Dr. Fisher's paper. Wylie suggests condensing
the material on the less bright meteors.

KG II 366.1071

cont. (p.2).

2

Fireball Report

1925-1932

typed

by William Fisher

Note (typed) to Dr. Wylie from Dr. Shapely, October 3, 1933 regarding Fisher's paper.

Last Page: "The Stars in Our Universe"

Seems to be chapter in astronomy book for beginners or children, etc.

End

FOLDER: "Copy" ~~Aug~~ August 10 - Oct. 16 total # pp. in folder (20) includes 2 small news P. clippings

Handwritten note to Dr. Shapely from Dr. Fisher 1927, Oct. 21.

" " " " " " " " " " " " 1927, Oct. 18.

typed A.P. Questionnaire on Fireball of Sunday Evening, 1927, Oct. 1

Press notice from the Harvard Observatory. (21 reports were received by H. Obs. in response to A.P. questionnaire).

Handwritten note to Shapely from Fisher, 1927, Oct. 27.

Handwritten draft by Fisher of Press Notice.

1928 Jan. 4

Handwr. note for Dr. Shapely from Dr. Fisher about planning of paper on Fireball Reports, reported by observers through A.P. Also included are Dr. Fisher's notes and "projected tables" for the paper, + "Miss Payne's" notes.

END.

KG 11366.1071

FOLDER:

Meteorites: penetrations excavated.

total no. pp. in folder: aprox.

(87)

- paper: "Excavated Meteorites" by Willard J. Fisher stamped Aug 9 + Aug. 13, 1934. "Attempts to relate meteorite finds to recent geological time." (typed, 7 pp).
- Handwr. note to Shapley from Fisher, 1934 Aug 3.
- Note to Fisher from Shapley, 1934 Aug. 13; saying that paper says claims to be about the distinction between finds and falls, whereas the chief results are on distribution of sub-surface finds + the relation to the time scale.
- Handwritten text of Fisher's Paper, "Excavated Meteorites".
- Earlier notes on Excavated Meteorites. ^{circa} Feb. 1933.
- Galley proof of paper. The Penetration of Iron Meteorites Into the Ground by Willard J. Fisher, 1933, Feb. 18. Typed 1932 Dec. 24. Includes tables + graph on logarithmic paper (16 pp., + graph).
- Handwritten text of above paper.
- Note to Prof. Palache, 1933 Jan 12, from Fisher, asking Palache to criticize iron meteorite pen. paper.
- Note to Dr. Bok, 1932 Dec. 31, from Fisher, thanking for criticism of paper.
- Note to Fisher from Bok, stamped Dec. 31, '32; comments on Fisher's iron meteorite paper.
- Graph dated 1929 Oct 15. showing Ground Penetrations of Stone Meteorites $s^2 = m^{1/2} \cdot \text{const.}$
- Page of calculations, Terminal fall and ground Penetration
- Page of " , dated Oct. 22 1930, Penetration of meteorite into the ground. (J. W. Fisher)
- calculations dated Sept 20 1930, Terminal Fall through air + earth penetration.

- graph, no date, 1929 Sept. 23, "Masses and penetrations into ground of stony meteorites."
- graph, 1930 Sept 30, "Penetration of meteorites, stones." (Slope = 23.3 Int. + 28)
- page of computation, no date. slope + intercept table for 7 meteorites
- 4 pages of The Pathfinder Star Maps, by Edward King, Cosmos Press, Cambridge, with computation on back of each page, dated Nov. 21, 1932.
- page of calculations, 1930 Oct. 5, "Penetration by Didion's equations"
- Table from "Penetration of Iron Mete." by Fisher, p. 7.
- 3 large graphs, dated "1930 Oct 20 and later", "1929 Oct. 15 and later", "1930 Sept. 12", showing Earth penetration of stony-meteorites.
- Large graph dated 1930 Oct. 21, showing Earth penetration of Iron Meteorites.
- 3 pages of calculations for above graphs.
- 8 handwritten pp. of paper dated Nov. 12 1932 by Fisher, "The Penetration of Meteorites Into the Ground"
- Note to Shapley from Fisher, 1932 Dec. 7, about typographical marks for designation of quarters, halves, & thirds. List of Meteorites on Back.
- Table, "Earth Penetration of Stony meteorites," no date. 7 pages of this table.

FOLDER:

"Geminids"

total # pp. in folder: (49)

- 8 pages of tables of Geminids, dated Dec. 11-12 1934.
- W.W. Johnson, H. Hemmendinger, F. Watson,
- 4 pages of calculations by Johnson called "1934 Geminids"
- 3^{1/2} pp. calculations + tables of Geminids by Watson, 1934.
- 2 meteor record sheets, date on both: 12/11 - 12/34
Recorded by Johnson.
- 5 photographs of ? sky.
- 3 pp. of plottings + recordings by Watson, 12/9 - 10/34
- 8 pp. of " " " " " " " " , 12/11 - 12/34.

- 2 pp. plotting charts, no recordings.
- Note 12/9/34 "Watch EW"
- 4 pages Meteor Records observed by Hemmendinger on Dec. 9-10, 1934 on Oak Ridge.
- 2 small charts "Non Gem. 1936" obs. J.H.
- 4 large tables, "Gemoids 1936", obs. D. Hoffert.

FOLDER: DIAGRAMS.

(8) pages

- Kepler's Laws, I, II
- 3 pages of unlabelled diagrams
- "Cloud Levels and Thicknesses", Lindenberg.
- "Twilight"
- "Lunar Mid-Eclipse" 1898 VII 3 1898 XII 27.
- Graph 4 Seasons, Trappes.

FOLDER: MISC

total # pp.: (39)

- letter to Fisher from W.S. Eichelberger, Captain US Navy, U.S. Naval Observatory, Jan. 5, 1921. regarding the true azimuth of Polaris.
- 2 pp. calculation, Silberstein's Method of Ray Tracing.
- unlabelled diagrams (2)
- 4 pages computations
- table "Jena Glasses" NO and mean Disp.
- calculations, computing form
- diagram + computation, 1928 Aug. 6, 7, "Sphere Paraboloid"
- " " " " " 1928 July 23, "Circle"
- " " " " " 1928 July 23, "Any Curve"
- 5 pp. unlabelled computation.
- 2 pp. computation, cylindrical coordinates.

- Letter to Fisher from Taylor, Taylor & Hobson, L^{td}, Stroughton Street Works, Leicester. 24 June 1921. regarding purchase of a Telephoto Lens.
- letter to Fisher from Elgin National Watch Co., Chicago, July 20 1920, regarding repair of Fisher's watch.
- 2 pp. calculations etc.
- Note to Fisher from Alex McAdri of Blue Hill Observatory, 12 June '24, about sighting the Mather's Island lights. 2 pp. calculations.
- 13 pp. of unlabeled charts.

FOLDER: VISUAL VELOCITIES | 11 pages + Notebook

- Graph showing Relations of heights $\circ$ Path Lengths $\times$ and disc. of shower meteors.
- Handwritten paper, 1 page, April 6 - 1932 "Duration of a meteor flight" in Fisher's handwriting. Next page "physiological and psychological course of events"
- 4 pages headed "G. Hoffmeister, A. N. 194, p. 327. 1913." "Bestimmungen von Meteorbahnen"
- 1 pg., handwritten, headed "Paper for AAVSO, N.Y., May 1931. A comparison of computed and observed velocities of periodic meteors. Willard Fisher.
- 1 pg. computation, Relation of means, Apr. 24 1932.
- notebook entitled Eclipse Notes, 4 pp. recorded observations 19th century.
- small page computations, "Lunar Eclipses 1930"
- chart, "Lunar Eclipse", Apr. 13, 1930.

- Report, not in a folder, typed, carbon of printer's copy, "The Total Lunar Eclipse of August 14, 1924" by Fisher. 28 pp.
- loose page, one side writing (by Fisher?) about withdrawal from work. other side, computation: Conversion of Right Ascension and Declination to al. Latitude and Longitude.
- 7 handwritten pp, lists of companies.
- small page headed "Formulas" 1899-1900. (For changing Right Ascension and Declination to Celestial Latitude and Longitude.
- 6 pages trigonometric calculation headed "Campbell p. 31 Astronomy."
- 3 pp. calculation
- 7 pp. of notes, pinned together, tables and unlabeled computation, etc.
- Clipped together:
 - note to Fisher from H.S., Nov. 23, 1925, about sending out Harvard Circular 284.
 - Mailing list for Circular 284.
 - handwritten note to Fisher from A.S.P. Maunder, Sept. 1 1925, regarding cost of supplying "an electro of your map illustrations rating the conditions of a lunar eclipse."
 - Note to Fisher from H.S. about ~~printed~~^{printing his} paper using Quincey Fund.
 - Memo for Dr. Shapely, Aug. 14, 1925 "Total lunar Eclipse, 1924 VIII 14. Following memo is the first typed copy of the paper, with rough corrections, etc. 32 pp, total.
 - 5 large pp. charts of lunar Eclipse 1924 VIII 14. Chronology of Observations.
 - handwritten copy of paper "Total lunar Eclipse, 1924 VIII 14", 22 pp.

- loose pages:
- large chart, "Weather Observations at the time of the Lunar Eclipse of 14th August, 1924, from British ships."
- Index card: H. C. O. Meteor Trails, Plate AC 25327 (1a), Date Aug. 8, 1924³.
- page "App. for falling bodies", Nov. 12, 1915, handwritten notes.
- Pamphlet in German announcing publication of "Annalen der Physik" book; Titled "An unsere Leser."
- 2 pp. of notes dated Aug. 9, 1916, "Measuring Angles".
- page of unlabeled computation
- Stansico Correlated Acoustic Chart.

FOLDER: EQUAL ALTITUDES

- page of trigonometric calculation, Aug. 12, 1916.
- 3 pages
- chart "Time by equal altitudes"

FOLDER: TIME AND LATITUDE WITH Y LEVEL

- typed paper, "Star-Time Observations with an Engineer's Y-level" by W. J. Fisher, Asst. Prof. of Physics, University of the Philippines. 4 pp.
- small note card, trigonometry.
- 3 pp. computation, Latitude with Y-level, Latitude by $w + \alpha$ Hercules. 1920 VI 20.
- 4 pp. computation, α Hercules.
- 4 pp. " " , Star Boss 234, 72 Piscum, 5.9
Date 1919 II 9
- 21 pp. of scratch work, computation, etc. (some on tiny pieces of paper)
- 27 pp. of notes + computation of " α Pegasi 1919 II 2".
- Photograph: Y-level set up for determining time and latitude. Manila, 1919.

FOLDER.

Meteoric Procession 1913 Feb. 9.

- 6 pp. (small) handwritten notes about "the earth-shaking detonations which accompanied the passage of the meteors in Ontario"
 - paper, typed, by W. J. Fisher: "Remarks on the Meteoric Procession of 1913 Feb 9." 8 pp.
 - carbon copy of above, 8 pp.
 - page of trigonometric calculations.
 - 8 pp; handwritten copy of paper "Remarks on Meteoric Procession of 1913 Feb. 9."
 - 5 pp. charts on Heights, etc. of fireball ↑
 - Letter to Fisher from Chas. P. Orr. of Leander McCormick Observatory, University of Va, Feb. 21, 1928, regarding work done on the Meteoric Procession of 1913.
 - Note to Fisher from H.S., Feb. 20, 1928, regarding the "getting out" of "another batch of published notes."
 - letter to Fisher from P. C. Day, Meteorologist, U.S. Dept. of Agriculture, Weather Bureau. Feb. 4, 1928. in response to question as to cloudiness about 9:10 PM Feb 9, 1913.
 - letter to Fisher from P. C. Day, Feb 9, 1928, saying that enclosed are charts with the state of weather at 8 p.m. Feb. 9, 1913 entered there on.
 - above chart ↑
 - small page, chart of observer's stations, 1913 Feb 9.
 - same list, typed.
-

- note by Fisher, 1930 Nov. 29, stating which plates are needed for the completion of the catalogue of meteor photographs.
- page of computation for anticrepuscular rays observed at Cambridge, 1930 Sept. 10.
- page of trigonometric functions, one side; also diagrams of mirror set-ups for July 19, 1916.
- page of notes: "Method of difs. Arith. progms. of higher orders. From 8 714." Date July 29, 1916.
- page of computations of $\frac{n(n-1)(n-2)}{3!} = y$ by differences. on back of Medway High School report card.
- 2 pp. unlabeled computation. July 12, 1912.
- Notes + diagram: Rotation of the Horizon Plane with regard to Directions fixed in Space Aug. 28, 1916.
- Note to Webster's Dynamics - p. 159. Jan 29, 1912, 2 pp
- List of Meteor Plates needed for completion of the catalogue of Harvard Meteor Photographs. 1930, Feb. ¹² (+ carbon of list.
- List of Missing Meteor Plates, Feb 11, 1930.

Clipped Together: ~~galley proofs?~~

- 2 long pages of what appears to be an article by Fisher for a science journal. Title: Lunar Eclipses in General and in the Philippine Islands - Sept. 23, 1929.
- 5 typed pages of above manuscript.
- 5 handwritten " " " " " " " " " " " "
- 5 typed pp. of " " " " " " " " " " " ", rough draft.

- 10 pp. of graphs; "Visual Velocities of Perseids", 1932 May 18;
- "Perseid Velocities determined - Frequency by years", 1932 Apr. 2;
- "Geminids" - Relative velocity astronomical, mostly English observations, March 12, 1932; "Perseids", March 16, 1932; "Orionids", Apr. 13, 1932;
- "Lyrids", March 12, 1932; "Quadrantids", March 12, 1932;
- "Leonid Meteors", March 12, 1932; VN - It Cat. 611, Mar 17, 1932.

- "Visual Velocities of Perseids" 1931 Feb. 13.
- 6 pp. of charts; Frequency of Visual Velocities of Perseids, 1931 Feb. 13; Experimental form for meteor velocities, 1931 Jan. 20; chart (unlabeled) 3 pp; Periods and geocentric velocities of meteors.

Loose pages:

- 8 small pages of unlabeled computation.
- Note, handwritten, 3 pp., to Shapely from Fisher, 1931 May 1st, regarding Fisher's work on visual velocity of meteors.
- 2 pp. unlabeled computation
- 10 small pages of charts, notes, + computation: reciprocal velocity, etc.
- 4 pp. unlabeled notes, 2 computation, 2 lists.
- 6 pp. of computation on Perseids, ^{Lyrids, Quadrantids, Geminids, + Leonids.} including a table "Geocentric Velocities of Periodic Meteors" dates: April 28 1932.
- Graph: Leonid frequency curves, Perseid frequency curves, April 28, 1932.
- page of arithmetic, Orionids.
- 7 pp. of unlabeled computation.
- 17 pp. of computation, dated July + August 1931.
- In brown envelope: paper by Fisher, typed, "The Total Lunar Eclipse of 1927 June 15", 19 pp.
 - diagram of lunar eclipse, + photograph.
 - large weather map, lunar eclipse.

KG 11366.1071

FOLDER:

FIREBALL REPORT 1925-1932, WJ Fisher

- This manuscript, entitled "Bright meteors reported to Harvard College Observatory 1925-32", has already been summarized on p.1. It is here ~~enclosed~~ attached to a note to Shapely from Fisher 1933 Aug 30, in which Fisher states that this report has been the main part of his work since early June.

Loose Pages:

- computation 1930 Dec 2, Mass of an iron hemisphere equal in mass to that of air column displaced in passage from outside the atmosphere to surface of ground.
- 2 pp. (folded) unlabelled computation.
- 14 small pages of notes + computation, Artillery projectiles,
- Note in Fisher's hand, 1930 Nov. 6. "Is it possible that the collision of atom on atom may remove matter from the body of a meteor without fusion? What would be the effect on method of computation?"
- 23 "scratch" pages of calculations etc.
- Note 1932 Oct. 14 by Fisher: "Suppose an infusible object projected into the air with a cosmic velocity. Would its velocity be different from that of a fusible object, other things being equal?"
- Graph & Chart 1934 Jan 17 "Frequency of Detonating meteors, by final heights"
- unlabeled graph, Sept. 28 1932.
- 27 pp. of charts; A.G. positions of stars for E 4646 + E 4658, Precision Correction, Approximate Reduction, Parallax Plates - Refraction.

- 1931 Feb. 12
- Catalogue - chronological - for all meteor velocities, not arranged by showers, 25 pp.
 - 24 pages, charts of meteor velocities, 1931 Feb. 7.
 - 10 pages, crossed out charts of meteor velocities, 1931 Feb. 7
 - note from H.S. to Miss Woods Apr. 5, 1929 about ↓
 - 2 pp. notes
 - 8 pp., list of "journals and so forth that are to be stored"
 - 5 pp., chart - "H.C.O. Meteor Trails; Summary. 1923 XI 8 (WSF)"
 - 7 small pp., lists of MA plates, MB plates, etc., + computation for photo scale
 - List of Meteor Lenses
 - List "Instruments" 1924 IX 11
 - Chart "H.C.O. Meteor Trails - Series to Search" March 1923
 - 6 pp. computation, lenses + apertures.
 - paper, 3 handwritten pages, (Fisher), Problem: "To find a rough representation of the number of meteor trails which may be photographed under constant atmospheric conditions by a lens, in terms of the radius of its image circle, its aperture, focal length, and other constants.
 - 9 pp. of computation
 - 1 page notes labeled "Report - End of Dec."
 - Bulletin 788 of Harvard College Observatory, Concerning Spectroscopic Tests of Stellar Luminosity.
 - note to Fisher from H.S. about meteor plates.
 - 4 pages computation
 - page of notes, "Queries on Meteors"
 - page of computation.

Loose Pages:

- note for Mr. Hanson, 1933 Aug. 11, from Fisher. Says "work on globe."
- chart, small, Aug. 10, 1933: Centering error of brass pocket compass, property of HCO.
- notes, Apr 4, 1932: w + AK Johnston, computation.
- note, Sept. 29, 1933, "S.T. 0th = Min." chart
- chart, " " " , Stillwell Planisphere
- 6 pp. of notes entitled "Fireballs at Sea."
- diagram, "2 Meteor paths plotted on a gromonic chart"
- page of computation
- page of computation which determines the ratio of the two unknown sides of the station-meteor-station triangle.
- 8 pp. "Fireballs and Meteorite Falls" Literature Search Lists.
- "Watch Records, Clocks and Chronometer" - page of computation
- chart of meteor series & months observed. labeled "for Colloquium Apr 7 1925"
- Chart, Meteor Trails arranged by months, Ames & Howarth, July 31 1925.
- chart AC's and AM's.
- chart, HCO Meteor Trails, "made before the Ames & Howarth Plates were returned to the stacks."
- 2 pages, "Duplicate Photographs of Meteor Trails", 1924 I 22, notes.
- 3 pages, "Meteor Trails"
- 1 page, "Meteor Trails, arranged by months"
- " " " "Meteor trails, count by years."
- Notes, "The Fall of a Meteor", 1932 Feb. 24, for Boston Univ. astr. Club. " , 2 page.
- Notes, "Radcliffe College Astronomy I", 1930 Dec 18.

END.

4/13/84

KG 11366. 1072 - Pamphlet case (Fischer)

Among others:

Drafts of papers on fireballs; the Amherst collection;
the green flash
lunar Eclipse Projections
Talk on brightness of eclipsed moon.
stuff on lunar plates

.1073 Pamphlet Case (Fischer)

All meteor + fireball material

→ .1074 " "

Largely newspaper clippings - all meters

.1075

Plates w/ meters; other meter material

Also: Lunar eclipse Spectra; Brightness of Lunar Eclipses
1860-1922; Volcanic Eruptions - ms.

.1076

All meteor material - painting of a fireball

1076.

Pieces of "reduction of photographic observation" notebooks
1, 3, 10

More material on meters, fireballs.

1077. All meteor material

1078. All meteor material

11365.791

KG 11366.1080 ~

Observations ~ 1881 ff. by Peckering & Chandler

KG 11366.1079 [PAMPHLET CASE]

LABEL: "METEORS, I : LEONIDS, 1898-1899: CLIPPINGS"

DATE: - 11/13/97 to 2/26/01.

(undated note) "Mainly Clippings on early Leonid Meteor
☼ showers (1898-1899). Really should be
mounted if possible. Historic interest. Please
don't throw away - or if you ~~do~~ must,
please give them to me. - Dorrit Hoffleit.
(to) Archives or Dr. Hoffleit."

(two envelopes in fragile condition) [A] "Meteor Shower, November, 1898",
containing 71 articles from ^{new} papers
and journals ~~from~~ ^{from all over} the world,
[B] "Meteor Shower - 1899", containing
103 articles.

NOTE: rapidly deteriorating.

(loose papers)

NO KG 11366.1081

KG 11366.1081
(Pamphlet Case)

WILLARD J. FISHER:
METEOR REPORTS, ETC., ETC.

[1919 — 1934]

1 p. "DR. W. J. FISHER — EFFECTUALLY, HIS PROFESSIONAL
'DIARY' AT HARVARD OBSERVATORY"

notebook	OBSERVATIONS OF "DAWN AND SUNSET":	1/8/19 — 12/15/19 } and 1/8/20 — 1/13/20 }
"	"	12/21/19 — 2/21/20
"	"	4/2/20 — 3/23/21
"	" + LUNAR ECLIPSE	3/23/21 — 9/10/30

REPORT ON METEOR WORK (monthly) 2/14/25 ~~W. J. Fisher~~

	3/13/25	W. J. Fisher
	4/11/25	W. J. Fisher 5/30/27
	5/9/25	6/30/27
	6/6/25	7/31/27
	7/3/25	(1P) Supplement to Fin. Report (p. 38) 8/30/27
F.S. 7/31/25	8/—/25	9/30/27
(p. 43) "report of 7 th month (2P) Addendum, Tables + Diagrams"	9/19/25	10/31/27
	10/24/25	"/30/27
F.S. 12/31/25	12/31/25	12/31/27
	2/28/26	any month
	3/28/26	etc.
F.S. 4/30/26	6/30/26	June 1-17/1931
" 8/31/26	8/31/26	June 17 - July 31, 1931
" 10/30/26	10/—/26	through
Financial statement	11/30/26	Aug, 1934.
	12/31/26	
	1/31/27	June 1, 28 into to May/28
	2/28/27	
	3/31/27	6/30/29 continuity of (2) accounts
	4/30/27	

1924

- 9/5/24 (1) Memo: summary and tentative program for work on meteor plates.
- 9/5/24 (2) "Note on the Study of Photographed Meteor Trails"
- 9/10/24 (1) "H.C.O. Meteor Trails - Cooke lens, F/13, aperture 1 inch"
- 9/13/24 (1) Letter: Frank Schlesinger (Yale) to H. Shapley - requests Fisher's notes before making specific recommendations about meteor research projects; asks to meet Fisher.
- 9/17/24 (1) Memo: revision of notes on Meteor trails.
- 9/25/24 (1) Letter: F.S. to H.S. - questions Fisher's estimate of the number of trails to be found on plates.
- 10/4/24 (1) Memo: the relationship of the number of trails to properties of the lens; precision of trail determination.
- 10/7/24 (1) Letter: F.S. to H.S. - questions whether there is a whole year's work; suggests accurate estimate of trails (10/9/24 annotation by Fisher asking about limit of tolerance). "Perhaps it would be sufficient to record the raw measures on the trails and to let some geometrical metaphysic carry out the computations."
- F.S.
- 11/8/24 (1) Letter: W.J.F. to C.P. Olivier (U. of Virginia) - correction to "catalogue of energy transformations" in meteors, and suggestion that sound is not important in energy dissipation.
- 11/26/24 (1) Memo: velocity determinations by Elkin; and the kinetic energy of a meteor varies by mass loss and not by deceleration

(over)

12/5/24 (1) Letter: WJF to C.P.O. - comments on a report on meteor
photo properly, and on the Lindemann-Dobson paper; thank-you
for a copy of plates for examination.

12/17/24 (2) Letter: WJF to C.P.O. - comments on field draft of IAU report;
indicates will not attend Wash DC meetg.

12/23/24 (1) Index card: "Distribution of Meteor Trails"

1925

2/2/25 (1) Letter to JF to W. S. Adams (Mt. Wilson) - asking for a print of a plate containing a meteor trail.

10/14/25 (1) Time sheet: for Elizabeth Belcher.

10/20/25 (2) Memo: "houses available for Meteor Photography"

10/29-30/25 (1) Memo: Ladd Obs. observations
" w/ (?) "Equipment to be sent to Ladd Obs. + Program for photo. @ shower maxima, + list of residents "reliquarium"

10/30/25 (1) Memo: rotating-camera technique for getting "time of apparition"

10/31/25 (1) Time sheet: for Evelyn J. Alcox. (Oct)

10/31/25 (2) (Annual?) "Report on Met. Research" 1/17/25 - 10/31/25
~~10/31/25~~

note: Smith part by other.

11/11-13/25 (2) Memo: houses + met. observing.

11/28/25 (2) Memo: observations of "daylight meteors"

11/30/25 (1) Time sheet: for Evelyn J. Alcox. (Nov.)

1926

1/1/26 (1) Memo: on lenses.

1/11/26 Notebook: "H.C.O. Meteor Trails:
Records, Accounts + Lists
1/16/25 to 1/4/26
w/ summary of 7/23/23 - 1/16/25

1/14/26 (1) Time Sheet for Eddy + J. Alcox (Dec, 1925)

1/27/26 (1) Memo: fireball class + questionnaire.

3/15/26 (1) Memo: "12/29/25 - Hornell (N.Y.) Fireball, Prelim. Values"

4/16/26 (2) letter WJF to C.P.O. - Meteor Comm. of AAS + public help
in obs (esp AAAS)

4/16/26 (1) Suggested questionnaire on Fireballs (7 ques.)

4/17/27 (2) (Special) Report on Meteor Work (for Nat Acad.)

7/1/26 (2) Summary of Conference 4/29/26 - 7/1/26 @ fireball
site + report.

7/7/26 (1) Letter: HS to WJF - proposing publ. of met. research
report in monograph, for disc. of conditions for continuing
work + funding.

7/24/26 (2) Letter: WJF to HS (see p. 39)
7/24/26 (2) Outline
7/24/26 (2)
" (2) + outline w/ sample classification

~~7/5/24 (1) Memo: velocity determinations by Elkin, and kinetic energy of meteor variables by mass loss and not by deceleration.~~

8/23/26 (1) Report of Met. Comm of AAS (received)

8/23/26 (1) Receipt of \$200

10/30/26 (3) letter: F.S. to H.S. + note by WF to H.S. funds of amateur obs's.
11/1/26

11/12/26 (1) Note: rough data @ AC + AAS plates, namely, frequency of tracks on plates.

11/13/26 (2) "Meteoric Problems" — "considered w/ regard to results solely, independent of expense".

12/10/26 (2) Note: getting the public to help w/ obs's; cataloging the Amherst Collection (~1100 items)

1927

1/8/27 (1) Note: Russian class of radiants

1/14/27 } (4) Note: "special researches suggested"; published, *Smithy* @ Andert Cell.
1/15/27 }

2/21/27 (1) Note: proposal for ^{work for} Redcliffe students for following year.

3/1/27 (1) Receipt for \$100.

4/15/27 (1) "Report on Met. Work, 1927 Apr. 15"

5/5/27 (1) ^{received} Memo: approval & payment of WJF in June, 1927.

9/10/27 (2) Letter: D. J. Flanagan (Boston) to A. L. Lowell
— telescopes make atmosphere invisible (e.g. terr. lenses)
+ ^{thus} vision for atmos, + is inhibited;
exp. w/ lamp signal.

9/29/27 (1) Note & introductory letter

9/15/27 (1) Note: introductory A notice

9/15/27 (3) Notice: "Fireballs of 1927 Aug. 10" - eds w/ request to public to note time of falls if possible.

1928

1/31/28 (1) Note: on Southern Meteor Observations

5/1/28 (1) Note: Table of comparison of Shower radiants w/ Comet radiants

8/24/28 (1) Note: "Meteor Problems" ^{introducing} "introducing very exact measurement in computing"

8/28/28 (2) "Met. Problems"

10/19/28 (1) Note: Observ^{ed} + Photograph^s of meteor^s

12/7/28 (1) Note: ^{introducing} circular @ Hist. research

12/27/28 (1) Note: introducing - Chinese

4/4/29 (2) Note: ^{findings of} met. work from 929
J.L. Smith ~~Smith~~ ^{Smith}

8/15/29 (2) Note: Hist. research problem.

9/30/28

(3) "Notes in Director's Annual Report"

9/30/27 - 9/30/28

~~10/29-30/25~~ + ~~10/4/24~~ + ~~11/26/24~~ + 19 + ~~11/12/26~~ + ~~12/23/24~~ + ~~10/30/25~~ + ~~1/27/26~~ + ~~11/28/25~~ + ~~11/11-13/25~~

Checklist

240 items

220

20

①

10/29-30/25		hadd obs.	(2 items)	25
?		Radio Talk		?
10/4/24		Memo		24
?		Football article		?
11/26/24		Memo		24
?		Met. Photo		?
?	45	Art. Summary		?
8/20/?		AY Plates		?
?		File card		?
3/15/26		Memo		26
1/1/26		"		26
R (8/23/26)		AAS report		26
8/23/26		Receipt		26
?	44	Metcalf plates		?
?		Qeminids (2 copies)		?
11/12/26		Note		26
?		Card heading		?
12/23/24		Trails		24
9/5/24		Memo		"
10/30/25		"		25
1/27/26		"		26
11/28/25		"		25
11/11-13/25		"		"
1/4/?		Measurement		?
11/13/26	43	Memo		26
7/10/24		"		24
? 7th month		Report		?
?		Certificate		?
10/20/25		Memo		25
?		Trails		?
9/17/24		Ken's Memo		24
?		Ken's		?
9/5/24		Memo		24
4/29/26 - 7/1/26		Summ. of Corresp.		26

?	Outline	?
7/24/26	Memo	26
?	notes	?
10/7/24	w/ annotated	24
9/25/24		24
9/13/24		24
?	(42) Wolf	?
4/16/26		26
4/16/26		"
12/17/24		24
?	Trails	?
12/5/24		24
11/8/24		"
2/2/25		25
?	Receipt	?
4/17/26		26
11/7/25 - 10/31/25		25
1/14/26	Timed	26
11/30/25	"	25
10/31/25	"	"
10/14/25	(41) "	"
10/30/26	Fin. St.	26
8/31/26	"	"
6/30/26	"	"
12/31/25	"	25
7/31/25	"	"
2/14/25	MR	X
3/13/25		X
4/11/25		X
5/9/25	(40)	X
4/6/25		X
7/3/25		X
8/?/25		X
2/10/25		X

10/24/25	MR	25
12/31/25		X
2/28/26		X
3/28/26		X
4/30/26		X
8/31/26		X
10/?/26		X
11/26	MR	X
12/10/26	Note	"
12/26	MR	X
1/2/27	Note	27

==

2/27	MR	27
3/1/27	Receipt	"
?	Cart.	?
3/27	MR	27
4/27	"	27
4/15/27	Report	"
?	Projects	?
5/27	MR	27
(7/5/27)	#	"
6/27	MR	27
7/24/26	Outline	26
7/24/26	letter	"
(7/24) 7/7/26	"	"
?	Comm.	?

==

Rec. (7/24)

7/27	MR	27
7/27	Suppl.	"
8/27	MR	27
9/15/27	Memo	"
?	Notes	?
1/31/28	notes	28
2/10/27	letter	27
2/29/27	"	"

38

9/27	MR	27
10/27	"	27
11/27	"	27
12/27	"	27
1/4/28?	Movie outline	?
1/28	MR	MR
2/28	"	MR
3/28	"	MR
?	heya d	?
?(1928)	Summ.	?
<hr/>		
5/1/28	'	28
?	Balls	?
?	"	?
?	"	?
4/28	MR	MR
5/28	"	MR
4.1/28 (37)	note	"
4/28	MR	MR
7/28	"	MR
8/28	"	MR
8/28/28	"	"
8/24/28	"	"
9/28	MR	MR
10/28	"	MR
> 9/30/28?	note on heart	"
10/19/28	note	"
11/28	MR	MR
12/28	"	MR
?	Appeal	?
12/7/28	note	28
?	China	?
12/28/28	"	28
1/29	MR	MR
2/29	MR	MR

3/29	MR	MR
4/29	"	MR
5/29	"	MR
6/29	"	MR
7/29	"	MR
4/30/29	note	"
8/15/29	"	"
4/4/29	"	"
8/29	MR	MR
9/29	"	MR
10/29	"	MR
11/29	"	MR
12/29	"	MR
1/30	"	MR
2/30	"	MR
3/12/30	Met.	"
3/30	MR	MR
4/30	"	MR
5/30	"	MR
6/30	"	MR
7/30	"	MR

8/29/30	note	"
8/30	MR	MR
9/2/30	note	"
9/10	MR	MR
10/30	"	MR
?	??	?
? (11/30)	Report	?
11/30	MR	MR
5/4/31	note	31
?	N.E.	?
12/30	MR	MR
1/31	"	MR
2/31	"	MR

(6)

3/31	MR	BA
4/31 (36)	"	WR
4/18/31	Photo	"
5/31	MR	WR
6/31	Report	WR "
6/17/31	MR	WR
?	Journal	?
7/31	MR	WR
8/31	"	WR
9/31	"	WR
10/31	"	WR
"/31	Note	WR "
"/31	MR	WR
12/29/31	Note	"
12/31	MR	WR
1/32	"	WR
2/32	"	WR
3/32	"	WR
4/13/32	Note	"
4/32	MR	WR
5/32	"	WR
6/32	"	WR
7/32	"	WR
8/32	"	WR

==

> 1934 Ag	Memo ASC	34+
1/27	MR	BA
10/30/26		26
11/1/26		"
1/14/27		27
1/15/27		"
8/34	MR	BA
7/34	"	WR
6/34	"	WR
5/34	"	WR

4/34 (33)	MR	MR
3/34	"	W
2/34	"	W
1/34	"	W
12/33	"	W
11/33	"	W
10/33	"	W
10/15/33	note	"
?	list	?
10/16/33	note	"
9/33 } ? }	MR	W
	Agenda	?
8/33	MR	W
7/33	"	W
6/33	"	W
5/33	"	W
5/15/33	meteorite	"
4/33	MR	W
3/33	"	W
11/9/33	Reform	"
2/21/27	Redcliffe	27
2/33	MR	W
1/33	"	W
12/32	"	W
Nov (12/2/32)	Bureau Report	"
11/32	MR	W
10/32	"	W
9/32	"	W
10/20/32	note	"
10/6/32	Memo	"

==